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**Scientific applications, end-user, and
observation requirements for the
CAIRT mission**

TN-1

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>This Technical Note summarizes scientific and societal applications, user needs, and observational requirements for the CAIRT mission. Where available and applicable, existing user requirements are compiled and assessed. In addition to CAIRT's primary (and secondary) science objectives, further applications for science and society are identify and their observational needs discussed. Existing observations and gaps in observations are identified and the unique contribution of CAIRT highlighted. Requirements for level-2 targets are derived from the scientific literature and existing user requirements, where applicable.</p>		
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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and Methodology

This Technical Note TN-1 prepared under the ESA CAIRT PerReC contract provides a survey and assessment of scientific applications, end-user and observation requirements for the CAIRT mission. Its scope is defined through the PerReC Statement of Work:

- TN-1 shall include a brief description of the methodology/ies used for the task.
- TN-1 shall include examples from a broad portfolio of applications.
- TN-1 shall include a gap analysis clearly identifying areas where CAIRT provides a unique opportunity and significant scientific development as an ESA Earth Explorer Mission.
- TN-1 shall include due consideration of needs for climate applications, including change and trend detection, and requirements associated with generating Climate Data Records (e.g. needs in terms of random and total uncertainty, bias, stability, statistical properties of the signal and interpretation of the requirements, etc.).
- TN-1 shall include analyses of the known or expected variability of CAIRT L2 and higher-level products across a range of spatial and temporal scales relevant to the science and mission objectives.
- TN-1 shall include a critical discussion of CAIRT L2 and higher-level products and their maturity to justify their production with respect to scientific applications and user needs. Challenges and risks shall be clearly identified for each product (primary and secondary). A final list of primary and secondary products shall be established with an evidence-based summary of their SRL.
- TN-1 shall include a section outlining the science case for secondary mission products, associated observation requirements, preliminary evaluation of feasibility, and their uptake into Phase A performance assessments in subsequent tasks.
- Contradictions found between different user needs and applications shall be highlighted and harmonised, and where applicable, the driving needs shall be established or confirmed.
- TN-1 shall include a critical discussion of MRD requirements and definitions with respect to scientific applications and user needs.
- TN-1 shall include a prioritisation of observation requirements where possible and applicable.
- TN-1 shall provide justifications for *all* observation and L2 product requirements, prioritising insufficiently defined or justified requirements, and including any additional analyses as needed.
- TN-1 shall identify missing observation and L2 product requirements, if any.
- TN-1 shall include a critical discussion of the CAIRT observing system concept(s) with respect to scientific applications and user needs, including potential synergies with other satellite missions.
- TN-1 shall include a documentation and justification of key processing requirements and/or other developments needed (i.e., not linked to the CAIRT mission space and ground segments) to meet the CAIRT science objectives or science/user needs/requirements¹⁰.
- TN-1 shall include a table demonstrating traceability from scientific user needs and applications to CAIRT L2 and higher-level products that can be used to update the MRD.
- TN-1 shall be prepared in a manner suitable to be used as input to the consolidation of the CAIRT MRD, as evidence to demonstrate the evolution of CAIRT from SRL-4 to SRL-5 and as part of the inputs to the Report for Mission Selection to be presented at the EE11 User Consultation Meeting.

The assessment of scientific applications and end-user needs is based on published user requirement documents, peer reviewed literature and analyses performed in CAIRT SciReC and PerReC.

We have consulted the input from the wider scientific community and it is planned that this TN will be reviewed by members of the scientific community that are not directly involved in CAIRT studies.

1.2 *Applicable reference documents*

The following reports are specifically considered to trace broader user requirements:

- ESA LOLIPOP CCI URD (Fabiano et al., 2024)
- ESA O3 CCI URD (van Weele, 2021)
- ESA water vapour CCI URD (Hegglin et al., 2019)
- ESA Operoz report (van Weele et al., 2015)
- ESA Mesosphero report (Rapp et al., 2015)
- GAW-159, The Changing Atmosphere (GAW-159, 2004)
- GCOS-245 (GCOS-245, 2022)

1.3 *Community feedback*

Members of the wider scientific community have provided input or feedback for user needs and requirements:

- Diagnosing atmospheric transport and circulation from long-lived trace gases:
 - Hella Garny, LMU Munich and DLR, Germany.
 - Gabriel Chiodo, IGEO-CSIC, Madrid, Spain
- Coupling with upper atmosphere
 - Miriam Sinnhuber, KIT, Germany
- Input of pollutants and aerosol precursors
 - Sergej Khaykin, LATMOS-IPSL, France
- Supporting the Montreal Protocol
 - Sophie Godin-Beckmann, France
 - Martyn Chipperfield, U Leeds, UK
- Assimilation for NRT
 - Elias Holm, ECMWF
- Improving retrievals of tropospheric gases
 - Daan Hubert, BIRA-IASB, Belgium
- Volcanic ash detection
 - Stefano Corradini, Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV), Italy
- Geoengineering
 - Simone Tilmes, NCAR, USA
- OCS and biospheric gross primary productivity
 - Marc van Hobe, Jülich, Germany

2 Primary Science Objectives of the CAIRT Mission

The CAIRT mission targets the middle atmosphere, from the upper troposphere (at about 5 km altitude) to the lower thermosphere (at about 115 km altitude). The middle atmosphere plays an important role in the climate system, as it connects distant regions, including coupling to the near-Earth space environment. It provides predictability on time-scales beyond typical weather time-scales, which makes it of importance for medium-range (on the time-scale of days) to sub-seasonal and seasonal (on the time-scale of months) forecasts. Changes in the middle atmosphere composition and its aerosol loading exert a critical forcing of surface climate, which makes it important in the context of natural climate variability through solar variability and volcanic eruptions, but also for proposed intentional climate interventions through solar radiation management by the release of particulates into the middle atmosphere.

The CAIRT mission is responding directly to ESA's 2015 Living Planet Strategy, as well as ESA's new 2024 Earth Observation Strategy "Earth Action for Tomorrow's World". CAIRT directly addresses the 2015 Living Planet Strategy Challenges on *Interactions between changes in large-scale atmospheric circulation and regional weather and climate* (Challenge A4), *Changes in atmospheric composition and air quality, including interactions with climate* (Challenge A3), and *Impacts of transient solar events on Earth's atmosphere* (Challenge A5). CAIRT's focus on couplings in our changing atmosphere is recognized as one of the high-level Science Themes of the new 2024 Earth Observation Strategy (ST-VI: *Interfaces and coupling in the Earth System*). Likewise, CAIRT's objectives make important contributions to the other high-level Science Themes, such as *Energy Fluxes* (ST-III) and *Extremes and Hazards* (ST-V).

The importance and timeliness of future limb observations has been highlighted by several international bodies, including the World Meteorological Organization in its 2022 Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) implementation plan. CAIRT data will fill a major gap in the monitoring of essential climate variables, in support of the Paris Agreement on climate change and the Montreal Protocol for protection of the ozone layer. The Montreal Protocol is not only safeguarding the ozone layer, but is in fact the most successful climate treaty to date: the control of ODS and HFCs under the Montreal Protocol and its amendments (in particular Kigali) have achieved a reduction in CO₂ equivalent emissions surpassing any other climate treaty to date. Moreover, the Montreal Protocol and its underpinning assessments are continually evolving to address new challenges to the ozone layer. For example, in the absence of an international treaty on possible geoengineering by solar radiation management, the Montreal Protocol is already providing a framework to assess potential adverse effects of this intervention through interactions with the ozone layer. Changes in the middle atmosphere circulation as a result of increases in greenhouse gas concentrations and the recovery of ozone depleting substances (e.g., (Abalos et al., 2019)) have a first-order effect on the recovery of the stratospheric ozone layer and are thus assessed under the WMO/UNEP Assessment of Ozone Depletion in support of the Montreal Protocol. CAIRT's primary science objectives, its user needs and applications are directly responding to these societal challenges in the gaps in observing and understanding the on-going processes and coupling throughout the middle atmosphere.

2.1 Diagnosing atmospheric transport and circulation from long-lived trace gases

CAIRT's Primary Science Objective 1 is to diagnose the changing atmospheric circulation between the upper troposphere and the lower thermosphere, through observations of temperature, long-lived trace gases and derived age-of-air, from the global scale down to spatial scales associated with mixing and exchange processes. The recent ESA LOLIPOP CCI on "other long-lived greenhouse gases" has compiled a user requirement document for long-lived greenhouse gas profile data in the upper troposphere, stratosphere

and mesosphere. According to the LOLIPOP URD, highest user interest is in the gases N₂O, SF₆, CFC-11 and CFC-12 (in that order), followed by CCl₄ and HCFC-22. Table 1 provides the user requirements from the ESA LOLIPOP CCI URD for the application of model evaluation, data assimilation and the calculating of radiative forcing. These requirements will not be identical to the requirements for the diagnosis of atmospheric transport and the calculation of age-of-air, as discussed in the following. (Note that these long-lived greenhouse gases which have received highest priority in the LOLIPOP URD are the CAIRT primary L2 target species for diagnosing atmospheric transport, with the exception of CCl₄. CCl₄ has not been included as a primary target for CAIRT, as for diagnosing atmospheric transport it is largely redundant with the other long-lived trace gases.) LOLIPOP user requirements for deriving emissions of these gases through inversion are not included here as this is a very different application area, outside of CAIRT's science objectives.

Table 1. User requirements for selected long-lived greenhouse gases as given by the ESA LOLIPOP CCI URD (2024).

Species of interest	N ₂ O, CFC-11, CFC-12 SF ₆ , CCl ₄ , HCFC-22
Application area	Model evaluation, data assimilation, radiative forcing
Horizontal resolution	Few degrees
Vertical resolution	1-3 km (less in upper atm)
Vertical extension	Troposphere to mesosphere
Accuracy	10% (better at 2-5%), N ₂ O 0.1 ppb
Additional requirements	Stability over time (no value) and assessment of systematic errors

The N₂O accuracy requirements by LOLIPOP of 0.1 ppb (less than 0.1% relative accuracy in the lower stratosphere) are based on GCOS-245 (2022) and primarily reflect user needs for tropospheric N₂O where variability is small.

The LOLIPOP CCI URD also includes an inventory of satellite observations of these long-lived greenhouse gases. For N₂O, which is the best covered species of this list, ongoing satellite profile observations are available from ACE-FTS, Aura-MLS and Odin-SMR, with MLS and Odin facing the end of their operational lifetime. For all other long-lived tracers of this list, ongoing satellite profile observations are based only on ACE-FTS, which as a solar occultation instrument has naturally limited geographical coverage. Total column information provided by the operational IASI satellite instruments has very limited utility for deriving transport in the middle atmosphere. This highlights the critical gap in available long-lived greenhouse gas observations, needed to diagnose atmospheric transport, and the unique opportunities for CAIRT in filling this gap.

2.1.1 Age-of-air in the stratosphere

An overview of the distribution of age-of-air and spread between observations is shown in Figure 1, based on Garny et al., (2024). Figure 2 shows the spread in age-of-air from different reanalyses in comparison to observed age-of-air. The spread between models and observations and the uncertainty of available observations is in the order of +/- 1 year. To achieve a breakthrough in the observation of age-of-air in the lower stratosphere, observations with a total uncertainty of 0.25 years or better for zonal means are required.

Temporal variability of age-or-air associated with inter-annual variability, modes of climate variability (ENSO, QBO, ...) and decadal-scale changes are in the order of +/-0.25 years (Figure 3, see also Fig. 13 of Garny et al.

(2024)). Detecting and quantifying changes of age-of-air requires (zonal and monthly mean) observations with a total uncertainty of less than 0.25 years, ideally at a total uncertainty of 0.1 years.

Figure 1. Mean age profiles averaged over high-latitudes (60°-90°), mid-latitudes (30°-60°) of each hemisphere, and tropics (30°S-30°N) from SF₆ satellite data (MIPAS, gray dashed line uncorrected mean, solid line sink-corrected mean, and gray shading displays range of ±1 standard deviation of the sink-corrected data) and from ACE (darkgreen, shown is only the sink-corrected mean) and averaged over available balloon flights (blue dotted: SF₆ mean ages; blue solid: SF₆ mean ages with the sink correction applied; red: CO₂ mean ages) and averaged over available aircraft flights (light-blue dotted: SF₆ mean ages; light-blue solid: SF₆ mean ages with the sink correction applied; magenta: CO₂ mean ages). From (Garny et al., 2024).

Figure 2. Mean age-of-air in 2002 - 2007 by the BASCOE TM driven by five reanalyses (colour solid lines) versus in-situ observations (symbols) with their 1σ uncertainties (grey shading). The five reanalyses are ERA-I (blue), MERRA-2 (red), MERRA (pink), JRA-55 (purple) and CFSR (green). The modeled AoA fields are corrected so that mean age = 0 at the tropical tropopause (100 hPa). (a) AoA at 50 hPa with aircraft observations of CO₂ (Andrews et al., 2001); (b) AoA in the tropics (10 $^{\circ}$ N - 10 $^{\circ}$ S) with aircraft observations (Andrews et al., 2001); (c) AoA in the northern mid-latitudes (35 $^{\circ}$ N - 45 $^{\circ}$ N) with balloon observations (Engel et al., 2009) and (d) AoA gradient between the northern mid-latitudes and tropics (Chipperfield et al., 2014; Neu et al., 2010). Figure from (Chabrillat et al., 2018), as reproduced as Fig. 5-27 in (Monge-Sanz et al., 2022).

Figure 3. Time evolution of AoA averaged from 30 hPa to 5 hPa (approximately 24 km to 36 km) in the southern (50° S - 40° S, left) and northern mid-latitudes (40° N - 50° N, right). Solid lines show model output with color codes according to the legend shown in the left panel. Thin lines (left panel only; omitted from right panel for clarity) show instantaneous model output every 5 days while thick lines are smoothed with a one-year running mean. Northern mid-latitude symbols (right panel) represent values derived from balloon observations of SF₆ (circles) and CO₂ (triangles) with color code showing the latitude of the measurements and outer error bars including sampling uncertainties (Engel et al., 2017). Fig. 5-36 of (Monge-Sanz et al., 2022), adapted from (Chabrilat et al., 2018).

Age-of-air is not only a useful concept in a zonal mean picture, but can be derived from long-lived trace gas observations at the scale of individual airmasses and provides useful and important information for the transport and mixing of airmasses. An example of small-scale variability in age-of-air and trace gases derived from in situ aircraft observations in the Northern Hemisphere winter stratosphere is shown in Figure 5. We see significant variability of age-of-air at the 100 km scale. To resolve this variability, age-of-air observations with a total uncertainty of better than 0.5 years at the 100 km scale are required. These can be derived from a set of long-lived trace gases, such as SF₆, CFC-11, CFC-12, HCFC-22, N₂O (plus CH₄ and CO). The correlation between age-of-air and long-lived tracers sets the requirements for the total uncertainty in the long-lived tracers to reach a total uncertainty in age-of-air of < 0.5 years (Table 2). These values are consolidated by further studies as part of PerReC (Voet et al., 2024). Figure 4 shows the correlation between age-of-air and N₂O as given by (Linz et al., 2016). The relation is valid for N₂O levels between 50 and 300 ppb and based on aircraft and balloon data measured between 1992–1998, thus needs to be scaled if directly applied for other years to account for the growth in atmospheric N₂O concentrations with time.

Expected trends for age-of-air are in the order of 0.1 years/decade (Garny et al., 2024), thus are currently very challenging to detect directly from observations.

Figure 4. Parametrized relation between age-of-air (derived from in-situ measurements of CO₂) and N₂O as given by (Linz et al., 2016). The relation is valid for N₂O levels between 50 and 300 ppb and based on aircraft and balloon data measured between 1992–1998, thus needs to be scaled if directly applied for other years to account for the growth in atmospheric N₂O concentrations with time.

Table 2. Requirements threshold total uncertainty of long-lived tracers in the lower stratosphere to infer age-of-air with a total uncertainty of < 0.5 years, based on observed trace gas correlations.

Parameter	Threshold total uncertainty
Age-of-air	0.5 years
SF ₆	0.15 ppt
N ₂ O	16 ppb
CH ₄	60 ppb
CFC-12	30 ppt

Figure 5. Observed small-scale variability of age-of-air, SF₆, N₂O, CH₄, CFC-12 and (for comparison) O₃ in the lower stratosphere at about 14 km altitude on 26 Feb 2016 during the POLSTRACC campaign with the German High altitude and Long-range Research Aircraft HALO.

2.1.2 Mixing

The middle atmosphere circulation (the Brewer-Dobson circulation in the stratosphere) can be conceptually separated into two components: the (diabatic) meridional overturning circulation and the (isentropic) quasi-horizontal mixing. Different concepts have been proposed to diagnose the quasi-horizontal mixing:

- Through the concept of Lagrangian effective diffusivity (Abalos et al., 2016))
- Through the vertical gradient of age-of-air ((Linz et al., 2021)¹; (Gupta et al., 2023)).

- As a residual in the age-of-air budget ((Garny et al., 2014); (Ploeger et al., 2015b) (Ploeger et al., 2015a)

2.2 Wave driving of the atmospheric circulation

Science Objective 2 is to quantify the contribution of *gravity waves* to the driving of the middle atmospheric circulation, identify their *sources* and investigate their *propagation* and *dissipation*, through observations of gravity waves between the lower stratosphere and the mesosphere and at scales relevant for circulation change.

Atmospheric gravity waves (GWs) are three-dimensional waves, i.e. they have a three-dimensional wave structure and they propagate, in general, from lower to higher altitudes but laterally at the same time. They exist because if an air parcel is lifted to higher altitudes it finds itself in an environment of lower pressure, therefore cools adiabatically, is heavier than its surrounding and tends to sink towards and beyond its original level of equilibrium. Vice versa, if an air parcel is displaced to lower altitudes, it is warmer and lighter than its surroundings and tends to rise. Hence, in this dynamical process temperature, displacement (if visible e.g. in tracers) and vertical and horizontal winds are the main observables. For the eye gravity waves become visible when clouds form in the cold phases of the upward displacement.

Gravity waves are excited by a manifold of processes. Most prominent is flow over mountain ridges, the latent heat release by condensing water and fast upward movement in convective towers (from thunderstorms to tropical cyclones), and the generation in unstable larger-scale flows such as the polar vortex. These sources imprint basic properties on the excited waves:

The width and orientation of mountain ridges determines the horizontal wavelength and orientation of the excited orographic gravity waves ("mountain waves"), lifetimes of thunderstorms and resonances in the excitation determine the wave period of convective gravity waves, and also different instability processes generate typical wavelengths and wave periods of the gravity waves they excite. Very characteristic of the wave source is the speed with which lines of constant wave phase (e.g. wave crests/ wave troughs) are moving. Mathematically this phase speed is the wavelength divided by the wave period. In orographic waves, the wind flows over the mountain and generates a wave whose phases are not moving with respect to the ground - like a stream flowing over an obstacle. Convection impinges the atmosphere and excites waves which are propagating away from the source - like a stone thrown into a pond. Flow instabilities often generate fields of almost parallel wave fronts - similar to wind over a lake. However, at one point the analogy between surface waves on water and waves in the atmosphere stops: the surface waves are 2D, the waves in the atmosphere are 3D. This allows also for a wider range of potential wave parameters as 3D the waves are freely propagating. From observations we note two basic properties:

- Gravity waves are usually strongly localized above their sources.
- Several waves can coexist in the same volume of air.

Because of the localization, in describing gravity waves we often use the concept of a wave packet with a localization and (small) limited extent. Inside such a packet, the wave is described by its wave parameters. Spatially, even within a small localized volume, several waves may coexist, which then are distinct by their wave parameters. Note that there are the polarization and the dispersion relation, which allow to convert from one set of parameters to others.

Figure 6. Illustration of the wave parameters defining a plane wave. In addition to the geometrical parameters wavelengths (λ_z and λ_h) and wave direction α there is the wave amplitude ruling the minimum and maximum values indicated by color.

One set of parameters which provide a full wave description is (Figure 6):

1. The vertical wavelength λ_z
2. The horizontal wavelength λ_h
3. The horizontal direction α
4. The temperature amplitude T_{amp}

These parameters can then be defined for several coexisting wave packets (wave components; *wc*) at a given location in space (x,y,z).

Note that a wave packet needs time to propagate and that while a source is active it excites continuously new wave packets. Let's consider this for the example of a mountain wave: the wave structure over a mountain needs time to fully build up over the whole atmospheric range, may change in structure depending on the propagation velocity of the individual wave packets contained and may still exist at higher altitudes even when the source is not active any more. In other words, the wave structure grows from below and disappears from below. Key papers: (Fritts, 1984), (Kim et al., 2003), (Fritts and Alexander, 2003), (Alexander et al., 2010), (Geller et al., 2013), (Plougonven et al., 2020).

2.2.1 Gravity waves driving the large-scale winds

A propagating gravity wave carries energy and momentum. As long as the wave propagates conservatively this energy and momentum are only conveyed, i.e. we talk about an energy flux and a momentum flux (Mcintyre, 1981) Only when the wave breaks (or dissipates by other processes) this momentum is released and the background wind is accelerated or decelerated (colloquially termed "gravity wave drag"). Again, we can use the analogy of water waves: only the breaking waves at the sea shore really impact the swimmer.

Generally speaking, the amplitude of a gravity wave can grow until the very perturbation induced by the wave makes the atmosphere unstable. This can be either by wind shear between the opposing phases of the wave or by so strong heating in the downward displacement that convection arises. Obviously, there are hence two factors which initiate breaking: first, a large absolute amplitude causes large shear; secondly the

same amplitude causes a much larger shear if the opposing wind phases are closer to each other, i.e. if the vertical wavelength is shorter. The same argument holds for convective instability.

A wave can only persist if it moves. In particular, for a gravity wave the vertical wavelength is roughly proportional to its intrinsic phase speed, i.e. the speed of the phase fronts relative to the background wind. For illustration, in a mountain wave the wave fronts do not move relative to the ground (zero ground-based phase speed), but for this reason they have in the moving air the opposite speed of the background wind (finite intrinsic phase speed). Vice versa, where the wave propagates into a wind which is equal to the ground-based phase speed of the wave, the intrinsic phase speed tends to zero and so does the vertical wavelength, the wave breaks and releases its momentum. This is shown in the example in Figure 7 provided by (Plougonven et al., 2020). The atmosphere is therefore accelerated in particular in strong gradients of the background wind because many waves will encounter a breaking condition by a fast changing critical condition.

Thus, the community agrees on the main quantities to be observed (e.g. (Preusse et al., 2012) (Plougonven et al., 2020)):

- The momentum flux determines how much drag can be exerted
- The phase speed rules at which altitude the drag is exerted
- The direction of the wave vector and thus of the momentum flux is the direction in which the drag is exerted

Also, these variables can be calculated for an individual wave, i.e. are defined for each wave-packet location and each wave-component.

Table 4 shows the need for variables associated with the individual waves and their dimensions in the wave data files.

Figure 7. Illustration from (Plougonven et al., 2020) (their Figure 1) elucidating the relation between phase speed and GW mean flow interaction. The original Figure caption reads: Offline calculations with (De La Cámara and Lott, 2015) parameterization, using daily wind and temperature from a given month (October) of an LMDZ climate run. (a) Vertical profile of the total forcing of the flow (gravity wave drag, or GWD) in the latitude band derived (45–75° N). (b)

Fraction of the contribution of waves with different ground-based phase speeds (in 10-m/s bins) to the total gravity wave drag as a function of height. The white line denotes the mean horizontal wind speed.

Table 3. Overview of variables determined by a suitable wave analysis or inferred from the fits by applying GW physics.

Variable	content	unit	generated	dimensions
λ_z	vertical wavelengths	[km]	fit	t,y,z,wc
λ_h	horizontal wavelength	[km]	fit	t,y,z,wc
α	wave direction	[deg], clockwise from N	fit	t,y,z,wc
Tamp	temperature amplitude	[K]	fit	t,y,z,wc
GWMF (F)	vertical flux of horizontal momentum	[Pa]	polarization relations	t,y,z,wc
cϕ,intr	intrinsic phase speed	[ms ⁻¹]	dispersion relation	t,y,z,wc
cϕ,gb	ground-based phase-speed	[ms ⁻¹]	Doppler shift	t,y,z,wc

Table 4. Data will be stored on orbit-following coordinates which and a horizontal grid coarser than the retrieval grid. The along-track distance t here determines the along-track distance x.

name	dimension / coordinate	definition	unit	sampling-distance	range
t	dimension	running time	[s]		
x	coordinate	along-track distance	[km]	150 km	N/A
y	dimension	across-track distance	[km]	100 km	-100 km to 100 km
z	dimension	height	[km]	1 km	20 km to 80 km
lon	coordinate	longitude	[deg]	N/A	N/A
lat	coordinate	latitude	[deg]	N/A	N/A

It is helpful for our conceptual understanding to quantify and model individual waves. Note, however, that the impact of GWs on the large-scale wind is always the result of a multitude of waves in a given region or even in a zonal mean. Our means of diagnosis are hence summarizing. Phase speed spectra, intermittency distributions and zonal means represent the statistical distribution from many waves from many single sources and evaluated over an ensemble of locations. Figures allowing for the scientific interpretation of the GW distribution are zonal means, phase-speed spectra, wavelength spectra and global or regional maps. The maps are most closely to the original parameters and mostly a selection and plotting. The generation of such figures from the individual gravity waves is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Illustration how to get meaningful diagnostics for scientific interpretation: The wave variables defined in Table 4 have to be evaluated in ensembles, i.e. selected, summarized and binned in different ways as indicated by the various colored arrows.

It is the drag which ultimately facilitates the driving of the large-scale structures. Drag calculation can be performed for an ensemble (zonal mean or regional average and also using tools like a ray-tracer for individual waves. The calculation of drag for a single wave component in a spatial analysis is problematic and not suggested here.

2.2.2 Main variables and requirements

A list of science communities, their need of variables and diagnostics is given in Table 5.

Table 5. Needs of the various communities for individual variables (cf. Table 4) and inferred "ensemble diagnostics" (cf. Figure 4). Variables are determined for individual waves and defined for each location and wave component, ensemble diagnostics summarize over regions and/or wave components.

Nr	community	variables	ensemble diagnostics
1	Data science	$\lambda_z, \lambda_h, \alpha, T_{amp}$	zonal mean
2	Fundamental research on GW	$\lambda_z, \lambda_h, \alpha, T_{amp}, F, c\phi, gb$	$c\phi$ - α spectra, maps, intermittency, zonal mean, λ_z - λ_h spectra
3	Climate projection		$c\phi$ - α spectra, maps, intermittency, zonal mean
4	Weather forecast		$c\phi$ - α spectra, maps, intermittency, zonal mean, λ_z - λ_h spectra

The uncertainty estimations and performance assessments for the variables and ensemble diagnostics are listed in Table 6.

Assessment of variables:

As the problem of inferring individual GW modes is non-linear and difficult to linearize (at least for a single wave estimate), uncertainty estimates will be performed via Monte-Carlo simulation. The leading observation error is considered to be the detector noise. Accordingly, the uncertainty estimate will be based on applying noise to observation and perform a combined retrieval and S3D analysis. Evaluating this noisy pseudo-observation for several instances of the same event will provide us with the uncertainty. The

performance estimate is gained by comparing the S3D analysis of the retrieved pseudo-observations to the S3D analysis of the sampled data, i.e. of the true temperature residuals at the observation locations.

Assessment of Ensemble Diagnostics:

In ensemble diagnostics we compare regional or zonal mean evaluations. We expect that the influence of details of the analysis (e.g. the analysis volume) is not relevant in a statistical evaluation. The same applies for the incomplete coverage due to orbital tracks versus full coverage. Thus, we can test the effects of both sampling and retrieval process. In addition, for the zonal-mean GWMF we can also test the effect of the wave-analysis and the application of polarization relation per se, as the zonal mean of $u'w'$, i.e. zonal GWMF without the need of wave analysis, provides an independent test.

Table 6. Overview of uncertainty estimates via Monte Carlo (UE), propagated uncertainties of inferred variables (UP) assessment of performance (APS) for individual variables and APS for ensemble diagnostics. Note that ensemble diagnostics also allow for checking assumptions such as the polarization relations and for plausibility tests such as spectral filtering in wind shears. (*) - GWMF and groundbased phase speed should match their requirements in an ensemble evaluation. The uncertainties quoted here are to be taken as rough guidelines.

Variable	requirement	uncertainty	APS for variables	APS for ensembles
λ_z	10 %	UE	(retrieval+S3D)	sampling, (retrieval+S3D)
λ_h	10 %	UE	(retrieval+S3D)	sampling, (retrieval+S3D)
α	10°	UE	(retrieval+S3D)	sampling, (retrieval+S3D)
T_{amp}	15 %	UE	(retrieval+S3D)	wave-analysis, sampling, (retrieval+S3D)
GWMF ($ F $)	30 % (*)	UP		wave-analysis, sampling, (retrieval+S3D)
$C\phi_{intr}$		UP		sampling, (retrieval+S3D)
$C\phi_{gb}$	5 m/s (*)	UP		sampling, (retrieval+S3D)

To set this into a context, include a list of papers which have given error (or uncertainty)

Table 7. Previous work on error estimates from the GW community (Note that at the time of publication the distinction between uncertainty and error would likely not have been made). The column *variable / ensemble* denotes if the inferred uncertainty applies to an ensemble evaluation or for the parameters of an individual wave

reference	quantities	uncertainty / error	variable / ensemble
Ern et al. (2004)	λ_h , GWMF	uncertainty	ensemble

2.2.3 Heisenberg, the averaging kernel and resolution

The fact that we here use the picture of wave packets means that we are in close analogy with the wave-particle dualism of the quantum theory of light. In this analogy, the photon essentially means the localization of the object, i.e. is the analogon of our gravity-wave packet, the wavelength of the light is the analogon to the wavelength of the gravity wave. In consequence, we here deal with three different kind of resolutions which can easily be confused, but must not be mixed up!

Spatial resolution of the temperature fields and spectral cut-off:

The spatial resolution of the temperatures is determined by the pixel size in across-track direction and by the sampling distance (i.e. the sampling frequency) and the 2D(!) averaging kernel in the along-track direction. Note that first generating two separate 1D resolutions for the horizontal and vertical direction leads to highly misleading results. This spatial resolution determines the spectral cut-off to the shortest waves seen.

In our analogy we may associate it with the short-wavelength cut-off of a photo detector. It is not part of the wave-particle dualism.

Spectral resolution:

The spectral resolution is defined by the possibility to distinguish between two waves in the same volume (at the same location) by their different spectral characteristics (here in terms of λ_z , λ_h , α ; mathematically equivalent to the 3D wavevector k). Essentially one can take the spectral resolution from the corresponding Fourier grid, but under the assumption that only a few waves superpose a higher spectral resolutions can be gained. In general, a larger analysis volume leads to better spectral resolution.

The spectral resolution resembles the possibility to detect the wavelength of the light.

Spatial resolution of the wave product:

Essentially, every wave analysis assumes that the amplitude is constant inside the volume considered, i.e. all wave parameters determined are valid for this volume which defines the spatial resolution of the wave analysis. Windowing, wavelets etc. make this slightly more complex since these methods introduce weights for the location, but these are details.

The spatial extent of the analysis volume and hence the spatial allocation of the wave packet resembles the detection of the location of the photon.

Thus, in the end the paradigm known from quantum mechanics (Heisenberg's uncertainty principle) applies for all wave analyses: the product of spectral uncertainty and spatial uncertainty is constant.

1. One has to find a compromise between these two uncertainties applicable for the physical problem
2. The precise wave decomposition may be method dependent
3. Ray-tracing is kind of proof that our interpretation makes sense!
4. The calculation of momentum flux directly from winds without applying wave analysis provides a second, independent test

Regarding 2: For simple problems such as the superposition of a few plane waves S3D can be shown to reproduce these waves independently of the precise choices of the analysis volume. We use this in our unit tests.

2.2.4 Requirements on GW parameters

For the characterization of the GW spectrum with CAIRT, individual GW parameters (as seen in Tab X) are determined from the temperature observations using the S3D methodology. The parameters are required for deriving GWMF but further can also be used for deeper GW analysis. In order to perform meaningful science, the parameters need to be known relatively well within $\pm 10\%$ for the horizontal and vertical wavelengths λ_h and λ_z and $\pm 10^\circ$ for the wave direction α .

To assess the needed accuracy, we perform ray-tracing experiments. In ray-tracing, we solve differential equations to calculate the propagation of the GW through the atmosphere backward in time, which allows the estimation of the source regions of the detected GWs. The calculated trajectories of the GWs are strongly dependent on the GW parameters; thus, it provides an extreme case for setting requirements: if the ray tracing can be performed consistent with given uncertainties of the GW parameters, most other analyses will also be fine with the data. Figure 9 shows the effect of a change of $\pm 10\%/^\circ$ in wavelengths and wave direction. It can be seen, that vertical wavelength and wave direction have the strongest impact. In the perturbed cases, a lot of GWs do no longer trace back to Iceland, as in the reference. The waves above Greenland are more stationary and less impacted.

Of course, this is the worst-case scenario, all parameters shifted by a fixed amount. More realistically, the errors in the parameters are standard distributed around the reference value with a given width. For a better assessment of the impact of the error on the backward trajectories, we have conducted a Monte Carlo simulation, where the parameters are perturbed and backward ray tracing is performed. Each simulation was repeated 100 times to give a representative result. Figure 10a shows the resulting distance from the source location of the GWs (estimated from backward ray tracing of the reference run) for errors of 3 to 15% for the horizontal and vertical wavelength and 3 to 15° for the wave direction. The mismatch in source location is relatively small throughout the simulated cases. Even with $10\%/^\circ$ error (case C), the error in source location is below 300km for the median. This is still very reasonable, as most source regions are quite extended regions (e.g., mountain ranges, regions of jet instabilities). The attribution of a wave to a source region also depends on the horizontal wavelength itself, therefore, Figure 10b show the horizontal distance mismatch in terms of horizontal wavelengths. Even for $15\%/^\circ$ error, almost half the GWs trace back to within one wavelength of the reference. For $10\%/^\circ$ error, more than 75% are within 2 wavelengths, which would be sufficient to attribute the waves to a given region.

Lastly, we consider the full period of 2018-12-10 to 2019-03-31 statistically. Figure 9 shows the total GWMF during this period that can be attributed to orography as a heatmap. High GWMF is observed, for example, above Greenland and Mongolia at 35km (Figure 9a). In the backward ray tracing, the GWs focus on a few source regions: Greenland, Iceland, Scandinavia, and Mongolia. An error of $10\%/^\circ$ leads to a reduction in GWMF attributed as stemming from Iceland (Figure 9b), otherwise, however, the patterns are very compatible with the reference backward raytracing. Increasing the error to $20\%/^\circ$ deteriorates the source distribution quite significantly: only little GWMF can be attributed to Iceland and the hot spots of Greenland and Scandinavia decrease in

absolute attributed GWMF. Generally, the distribution is more spread out and not as clearly associable to mountain ranges (e.g., Mongolia).

Considering all of the above, the GW parameters should be known to higher precision than about 20% for the horizontal and vertical wavelength and 20° for the wave direction. An uncertainty of $10\%/^\circ$ would allow for meaningful backward ray tracing and further related analyses. Note again that the ray tracing is highly dependent on the wave analysis and, therefore, other analyses should perform well with an uncertainty of $10\%/^\circ$ for the wave parameters.

Figure 9. Effect of different wave parameters on backward ray-tracing trajectories of the waves shown in panel a at 35km altitude. Color shading shows the summed GWMF in a given bin at 35km (panel a) or at the altitude where the ray terminates (all other panels). Panel b shows the reference locations of the backward ray tracing, panels c & d, e & f, and g & h show the effect of horizontal wavelength, vertical wavelength, and wave direction, respectively. Reduced/increased refers to the values being perturbed by $\pm 10\%$ for the wavelengths and $\pm 10^\circ$ for the wave direction.

Figure 10. Distributions of mismatch in horizontal distance of detected GWs after backward ray-tracing compared to the reference run with sampled temperature perturbations. The cases A, B, C, and D correspond to standard distributed errors of the wave parameters of 3, 5, 10, and 15 % or °, respectively. For each case, 100 simulations have been performed in a Monte-Carlo-like fashion. The lines show the 1st, 2nd (median), and 3rd quartile, respectively.

Figure 11. Total orographic GWMF observed during the whole period 2018-12-10 to 2019-03-31 as observed by CAIRT at 35km altitude north of 40°N (panel a). Panels b–c show the estimated source region of the GWs shown in panel a by the use of ray-tracing. For panels b and c, the wave parameters have been perturbed by a standard distributed error of 10%/° and 20%/°, respectively.

2.3 Coupling with the upper atmosphere through downward flux of reactive nitrogen compounds

CAIRT Science Objective 3 is to investigate *upper atmospheric coupling* and concomitant regional surface climate variability associated with transient solar events and space weather through the *downward flux of reactive nitrogen* (NO_y) from the thermosphere, and its impacts on stratospheric ozone. NO_y, sometimes

also called “odd nitrogen”, is here defined as the sum of nitric oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), nitric acid (HNO₃), chlorine nitrate (ClONO₂) and dinitrogen pentoxide (N₂O₅), the latter one counted twice to account for the two nitrogen atoms in that species. The main and almost exclusive source of NO_y input into the middle atmosphere from below is through N₂O and following breakdown. This leads to a very compact anti-correlation between N₂O and NO_y in the lower stratosphere. In the thermosphere, large amounts of NO can be formed by ionization of N₂ from energetic particles and following ion-recombination reactions. Similarly, energetic particles in the stratosphere or mesosphere (e.g. from solar proton events) can result in local NO production. Depending on the physical and photo-chemical environment (i.e., depending on altitude, latitude, season and time of day), the partitioning of NO_y into the individual components differs.

2.3.1 Observing NO in the lower thermosphere

The maximum number density of NO is found in the high-latitude lower thermosphere at around 100 km altitude. Figure 12 shows a climatological distribution based on Odin-SMR observations. To provide an upper boundary for the amount of NO_y transported down into the mesosphere and stratosphere, and to investigate the coupling of NO₂ production with solar and geomagnetic variability, it is important to observe NO up to altitudes of 105 km, ideally up to 115 km. This drives CAIRT’s observation requirement for observations up to 105 km (threshold) / 115 km (goal).

Figure 12. Odin-SMR observations of NO concentrations in the lower thermosphere, between 2004 and 2016, shown as a function of magnetic latitude. From (Kiviranta et al., 2018).

2.3.2 Observing the flux of reactive nitrogen compounds (NO_x and NO_y) into the stratosphere

Figure 13 shows an example of the descent of NO_y rich air during high latitude winter from the MLT region into the mesosphere and stratosphere. Together with enhanced levels of NO, also carbon monoxide (CO) is enhanced. CO is formed in the MLT region from the destruction of CO₂. In addition, these airmasses are low in methane (CH₄). Excess NO_y can be detected and quantified through correlations with CO and CH₄. Simultaneous observation of NO_y, CO and CH₄ are thus required to quantify the flux of NO_y from the MLT region into the middle atmosphere. As the subsidence takes place in the winter high-latitudes, latitudinal

coverage including high latitudes (well beyond 70° North or South) is required. The numbers in the example shown in Figure 13 provide a guidance for the expected range of NO_y and CO volume mixing ratios needed to detect the subsidence of MLT NO_y.

Figure 13. MIPAS/Envisat observations of mesospheric subsidence of NO_y (top), CO (middle) and methane (bottom) poleward of 70°S. (Funke et al., 2014).

2.4 Input of pollutants and aerosol precursors

CAIRT Science Objective 4 is to quantify *lower atmospheric coupling* associated with the lofting or injection of natural and anthropogenic plumes of *pollutants and aerosol precursors* into the upper troposphere and stratosphere, their impacts on composition, and their crucial role for climate forcing and feedbacks.

2.4.1 Pollutants

The impact of smoke and pollution from wildfires on middle atmosphere ozone and radiative forcing is a recent emerging topic ((Solomon et al., 2023); (Khaykin et al., 2020)). Important pollutants and tracers for polluted air masses are carbon monoxide (CO) and peroxyacetyl nitrate (PAN). Carbon monoxide (CO) can reach mixing ratios of up to a few hundred parts per billion (ppb) in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere. E.g., the 2019/2020 Australian wildfire plume injected into the stratosphere contained CO mixing ratios of 200-400 ppb in a layer ~3 km thick (Figure 14), as measured by Aura-MLS (Khaykin et al., 2020). The stratospheric background of CO in the absence of plumes from the troposphere and descent from the mesosphere is at around 25 ppb.

Figure 14. Injection of a smoke plume into the stratosphere by the 2019/2020 Australian wild fires. **(a)** CALIOP attenuated scattering observations of smoke particles, **(b)** MLS observations of water vapour, **(c)** MLS observations of carbon monoxide and **(d)** GNSS radio occultation observation of temperature anomalies. From (Khaykin et al., 2020).

Satellite profile measurements of CO mixing ratios in the upper troposphere and stratosphere are currently available from Aura-MLS and ACE-FTS. There is so far no planned satellite mission that will provide CO profiles in the upper troposphere / lower stratosphere. With Aura-MLS coming towards the end of its lifetime and the limited geographical coverage of ACE-FTS, there is a critical gap in future stratospheric CO profile observation and a unique opportunity for CAIRT.

GCOS ECV Requirements for Precursors of Aerosols and Ozone ((WMO et al., 2022a) GCOS-244) has formulated requirements for carbon monoxide mixing ratio profiles (Table 5). These GCOS requirements do not explicitly specify the applicable altitude range.

Table 5. GCOS ECV Requirements for carbon monoxide (GCOS-244, 2022).

Product	CO mole fraction
Horizontal resolution	(G) 10 km (B) 30 km (T) 100 km
Vertical resolution	(G) 1 km (B) 3 km (T) 5 km
Temporal resolution	(G) 1 hr (B) 1 day (T) 30 days
Timeliness	(G) 1 day (B) 7 days (T) 30 days
Uncertainty (2-sigma)	(G) 1 ppb (B) 5 ppb (T) 10 ppb
Stability	(G) < 1 ppb / decade (B) 1 ppb /decade (T) 3 ppb / decade

Peroxyacetyl nitrate (PAN, $C_2H_3NO_5$) is an important air pollutant, produced in the atmosphere by oxidation of hydrocarbons in the presence of nitrogen dioxide. Because of its relatively long chemical stability in the upper troposphere it significantly contributes to the long range transport of reactive nitrogen. In pollution plumes PAN reaches volume mixing ratios of several hundred parts per trillion (pptv), with background values at 100 pptv or below. An example of an observed and modelled PAN plume originating from Amazonian biomass burning is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Peroxyacetyl nitrate (PAN) in the upper troposphere over the south Atlantic as measured by the GLORIA instrument onboard the German HALO research aircraft as a function of time (a) and compared to the CAMS analysis interpolated to the measurement locations (b). From (Johansson et al., 2022).

Being able to detect PAN in pollution plumes, to quantify its contribution and to validate models thus requires an accuracy of better than 100 pptv.

2.4.2 Stratospheric sulfur budget

The stratospheric aerosol layer consists primarily of sulfate (liquid H_2SO_4) droplets. They play an important role for atmospheric chemistry and radiative forcing. During volcanic quiescent periods the main sources for H_2SO_4 in the stratosphere are sulfur dioxide (SO_2) and carbonyl sulfate (COS or OCS). Measuring all three main sulfur species simultaneously would enable to close the stratospheric sulfur budget (e.g., (Günther et al., 2018)). Volcanic eruptions can enhance the stratospheric sulfate loading by orders of magnitude.

Figure 16. MIPAS satellite observations of liquid phase H_2SO_4 (a) and SO_2 (b) volume mixing ratios at different altitudes between 10 and 22 km. Observations have been averaged over 8 days and within 10° of latitude. Red triangle symbols represent known volcanic eruptions. Color scales restricted to 1000 pptv for H_2SO_4 and 300 pptv for SO_2 . From (Günther et al., 2018).

2.5 Radiative-dynamic-chemical coupling through ozone and water

CAIRT Science Objective 5 is to Resolve strong vertical gradients and fluxes of ozone and water vapour across the tropopause, facilitate the attribution of changes in middle atmospheric ozone, water vapour, and other constituents to changes in stratosphere-troposphere exchange, circulation, and chemistry, and improve our knowledge of the complex radiative-dynamic-chemical coupling governing our climate system.

2.5.1 Ozone and water vapour around the tropopause

Ozone and water vapour are the most important radiatively active gases in the stratosphere, with a particularly strong efficiency of changes around the cold tropopause. E.g. Solomon et al., Contributions of Stratospheric Water Vapor to Decadal Changes in the Rate of Global Warming, (Solomon et al., 2010). The large gradients of ozone and water vapour across the tropopause make detections by satellite remote sensing difficult, but are crucially important for the exchange across the tropopause. As an example, Figure

17 shows high resolution airborne lidar observations of ozone and water vapour around the tropopause during a tropopause folding event over the North Atlantic (Schäfler et al., 2023). The coincident observations of ozone and water vapour enable the identification of different air masses, affected at different degrees by mixing between tropospheric air (high in water and low in ozone) and stratospheric air (low in water and high in ozone). From these observations we can already estimate the required spatial scales and total uncertainties required to resolve these exchange- and mixing processes around the tropopause. The different layers have a thickness of about 1-2 km at horizontal scales of about 100-200 km (Figure 17, f). Capturing an important fraction of this variability around the tropopause thus requires coincident observations of ozone and water vapour at horizontal scales of about 100 km horizontally and about 1 km vertically. Ozone should ideally be resolved at a total uncertainty of about 100 ppb in the lower stratosphere and better in the upper troposphere, while water vapour needs to be resolved at a total uncertainty of about 10%.

Figure 17. Observations of water vapour (a) and ozone (b) in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere across a North Atlantic jet stream (c) by airborne lidar observations. Bottom shows a classification of air masses (e, f). From (Schäfler et al., 2023).

2.5.2 Quantifying the distribution of O₃ throughout the middle atmosphere

User requirements for ozone observations have been specified by GCOS (Table 6), WMO (Table 7) and ESA O3 CCI (Table 8). These requirements slightly deviate in detail, but all agree that vertically resolved ozone observations from the upper troposphere to the mesosphere are required with a horizontal resolution of 100 to 200 km and a vertical resolution of generally 3 km or better.

Table 6. GCOS target requirements for ozone profile observations.

Variable	Horizontal resolution	Vertical resolution	Temporal resolution	Accuracy	Stability
Ozone profile in upper stratosphere and mesosphere	100 – 200 km	3 km	daily	5 – 20%	<1%
Ozone profile in upper troposphere and lower stratosphere	100 – 200 km	1 – 2 km	4 h	10%	1%

Table 7. WMO requirements for ozone profile observations, divided into goal, breakthrough (B) and threshold (Th).

Region	Horizontal resolution (km)			Vertical resolution (km)			Accuracy		
	Goal	B	Th	Goal	B	Th	Goal	B	Th
Upper stratosphere and mesosphere	50	107.7	500	1	1.7	5	5%	8.5%	25%
Upper troposphere	50	107.7	500	1	1.7	5	3%	5.6%	20%
Lower stratosphere	50	107.7	500	1	1.7	5	3%	5.6%	20%

Table 8. Product requirements for limb-based ozone profile Climate Data Records taken from ESA O3 CCI URD (2016, their Table 9). The lower stratosphere (LS) extends from the tropopause to about 30 km, and the middle atmosphere extends from about 30 to 60 km altitude. The required coverage is global.

Quantity	Driving Research Topic	Lower Stratosphere	Middle Atmosphere
Horizontal resolution	Regional differences in the evolution of the ozone layer (radiative forcing); Seasonal cycle and interannual variability; Short-term variability	100 – 200 km	200 – 400 km
Vertical resolution	Height dependence of evolution of the ozone layer (radiative forcing); Seasonal cycle and interannual variability; Short-term variability	1 – 2 km	2 – 4 km
Observation frequency	Seasonal cycle and interannual variability; short-term variability	Daily – weekly	Daily – weekly

Accuracy in height attribution	Evolution of the ozone layer (radiative forcing), Seasonal cycle and interannual variability; Short-term variability	+/- 500 m	+/- 500 m
Accuracy for mixing ratio	Evolution of the ozone layer (radiative forcing)	8%	8%
Accuracy for mixing ratio	Seasonal cycle and interannual variability; Short-term variability*	16% (<20 km) 8% (>20 km)	8%
Stability	Evolution of the ozone layer (radiative forcing); trends	1 – 3% / decade	1 – 3% / decade

While ozone profile observations in the stratosphere will likely be available in the coming decades through existing, continued and upcoming instruments (list to be expanded and checked: OMPS-LS, ..., ALTIUS, ...), critical gaps remain for the UTLS region where vertical and horizontal gradients are large and in particular for polar ozone where UV/visible and solar occultation observations have only very limited coverage.

2.5.3 Polar ozone depletion

Substantial chemical ozone depletion occurs in the Antarctic ozone hole during spring, with important and robust impacts on atmospheric dynamics and surface climate (WMO). The Antarctic ozone hole is only slowly recovering during the 21st century because of the long atmospheric lifetimes of the ozone depleting substances. During particularly cold Arctic winters, over the past decades roughly at every 5 years, substantial stratospheric ozone depletion has been observed also over the Arctic ((WMO et al., 2022b); (Sinnhuber et al., 2011)). Recovery of Arctic ozone depletion is even more uncertain, because of the long-term radiative cooling of the stratosphere that may increase the possibility of severe Arctic ozone depletion and a possible increase in the strength of the Brewer-Dobson circulation that will lead to adiabatic warming of the Arctic lower stratosphere, decreasing the possibility of severe Arctic ozone depletion e.g. (Sinnhuber et al., 2011). A continued monitoring of polar stratospheric ozone depletion in the coming decades is thus of high importance, for improving the process understanding of the interaction of dynamics, radiation and chemistry and testing of models.

Simultaneous observations of long-lived tracers such as N₂O or CH₄ are critical to quantify polar stratospheric ozone depletion. A threshold total uncertainty in lower stratospheric N₂O by +/- 16ppt as required for SO-1 (and similar for CH₄) will be sufficient to diagnose the transport induced changes in ozone: N₂O decreases by about 50 – 100 ppb inside the Arctic lower stratospheric polar vortex at constant potential temperature throughout winter (Figure 18, (Sinnhuber et al., 2011)).

Attribution of polar ozone depletion to transport and chemistry and validation of the chemical mechanisms will require observation of additional species, most importantly ClO, ClONO₂, HCl, and HNO₃ (van Weele et al., 2015) - Operoz, Sec. 1.3.3). While observation of HCl is not possible through infra-red limb emission, ClONO₂ provides largely complementary observations. ClO and ClONO₂ should have a threshold total uncertainty of better than 0.25 ppb for vortex averages and HNO₃ better than 1 ppb ((Sinnhuber et al., 2011), (van Weele et al., 2015) - Operoz, Table 2.5). ((van Weele et al., 2015)- Operoz, Table 2.5, specifies ClONO₂ threshold uncertainty requirement of 0.1 ppb for the polar lower stratosphere.)

Figure 18. Arctic stratospheric ozone depletion in winter 2010/2011: Comparison of MIPAS/Envisat observations (red dots) and model calculations (solid lines) of (a) temperature, (b) ozone, (c) column ozone loss, (d) nitrous oxide, (e) nitric acid, (f) water, (g) chlorine nitrate and (h) chlorine monoxide. Gray shading with red and blue bounding lines indicate model results of a ± 1 K temperature change. All quantities are averages over equivalent latitudes north of 70°N at 475 K potential temperature. From (Sinnhuber et al., 2011).

The climatological stratospheric polar vortex edge is at about 70° latitude, i.e. observations of polar stratospheric processes will benefit from a coverage well poleward of 70°, although occasional equatorward displacements of the polar vortex will enable also vortex observations at lower latitudes. To resolve gradients across the vortex edge as well as inhomogeneities within the vortex a horizontal resolution of better than 200 km is required (van Weele et al., 2015) - Operoz, Table 2.5).

Most information on polar stratospheric ozone depletion has been obtained from in-situ ozone sonde observations and from satellite observations by MIPAS ENVISAT (2002-2012) and in particular the Microwave Limb Sounders (MLS) on UARS (1991–2001) and Aura (since 2004) and the Swedish Submillimeter Radiometer (SMR) on Odin (since 2001). Aura-MLS and Odin are at the end of their lifetime and expected to stop operations within the next two years, without any scheduled follow-on mission. This will leave a severe gap in the observational capacity for polar stratospheric ozone. Solar occultation instruments (such as ACE-FTS) have a very limited sampling of the polar winter stratosphere.

2.5.4 Detecting and attributing trends in O₃

Stratospheric ozone trends are in the order of 1%/decade in the upper stratosphere and less (and uncertain) in the lower stratosphere (WMO, 2022). Interannual and decadal scale variability in stratospheric ozone are about 2% for the 11-year solar cycle signal and about +/- 5-10% associated with the Quasi Biennial Oscillation (QBO). Detecting these decadal scale changes would require stability of ozone observations at better than 1% over a decade. However, while the mere detection of ozone trends will be possible with scheduled upcoming instruments like OMPS-LP, there is a critical gap in tracer measurements to attribute ozone changes to changes in transport/circulation and chemistry/composition.

2.5.5 Quantify the distribution H₂O throughout the middle atmosphere

Water vapour exhibits a large change in mixing ratio in the atmosphere, with strong gradients across the tropopause. The stratosphere is very dry, with stratospheric water vapour mixing ratios in the of about 3-4 ppmv just above the tropical tropopause and increasing with altitude in the stratosphere due to the degradation of methane oxidation. User requirements for stratospheric water vapour are formulated by ESA Water Vapour CCI User Requirements, based on GCOS (Table 9).

Table 9. GCOS ECV requirements for vertical resolved water vapour profile observations.

Product	Horizontal resolution	Vertical resolution	Accuracy (95% confidence level)	Stability
Tropospheric vertical resolved WV	25 km	2 km	5 %	0.3 % / decade
Stratospheric vertical resolved WV	100 – 200 km	2 km	5 %	0.3 % / decade

2.5.6 Detecting and attributing trends in H₂O

Interannual changes in stratospheric water, controlled by temperature variations at the tropical cold point tropopause, are in the order of +/- 0.5 ppmv (Figure 19). (Tao et al., 2023)) have analysed multidecadal variability in stratospheric water vapour. Stratospheric water vapour changes are typically in the order of 10%/decade.

Figure 19. Temperature control of water vapour entry at the tropical tropopause. Time series of deseasonalized anomalies in tropical cold point tropopause (CPT) temperature from GPS radio occultation (10°S–10°N) and equatorial (5°N–5°S) 83 hPa water vapour from Aura MLS. Fig. 5-3 from WMO (2022).

3 Secondary science objectives

User needs and requirements for secondary objectives have not yet been assessed systematically. These are not driving observation and measurement requirements of the CAIRT mission concept.

4 Applications for science and society

4.1 Supporting the Montreal Protocol

Ozone itself will be relatively well covered by future satellite missions, but for ODS, polar ozone depletion, subsidence from upper atmosphere and transport tracers there will be a serious gap after the soon expected end of MLS and ODIN, and an unclear future of ACE/FTS. Consequently, there is an urgent need for a new limb satellite like CAIRT. The 2022 WMO/UNEP Scientific Assessment of Ozone Depletion ((WMO et al., 2023)- GAW-278), 2023, p. 163) quotes *the need to “continue limb emission and infrared solar occultation observations from space” that are “necessary for global vertical profiles of many ozone- and climate-related trace gases” as one of the “key systematic observations recommendations”*. It should be stressed, that the WMO/UNEP Assessment process as requested by the Parties of the Montreal Protocol now has a mandate to assess the following topics directly relevant for CAIRT:

- Ozone Depleting Substances, including CFCs and halogenated compounds, N₂O
- Global ozone and ozone trends
- Polar ozone and related processes
- Stratosphere-climate connections:
 - middle atmosphere circulation
 - water vapour trends
 - volcanic impact
 - solar impact

- Stratospheric solar radiation management.

4.2 Improving retrievals of tropospheric gases

Height resolved limb observations can together with nadir observations provide important constraints for the retrievals of tropospheric gases. This is in particular important for the retrieval of tropospheric ozone, otherwise very challenging, as only about 10% of the total ozone column are located in the troposphere and about 90% in the stratosphere. Reducing the uncertainty in the stratospheric ozone contribution therefore has a strong impact on improving tropospheric ozone retrievals. Also, for other compounds, such as methane, better constraining the stratospheric contribution can help to improve the retrieval of the tropospheric distribution, including the quantification of emission sources.

4.3 Assimilation of CAIRT data for NWP, space weather and climate reanalyses

4.3.1 Water vapour in the lower stratosphere

Improving the representation of water vapour and ozone in the UTLS in numerical weather forecasting models has been shown to lead to significant improvements in meteorological predictions (Hogan et al., 2017; Monge-Sanz et al., 2022). Assimilation of water vapour data from Aura/MLS in ECMWF's forecasting system (Semane and Bonavita, 2025) improves long-standing temperature biases in the model through improved water vapour interaction with radiation, as well as sharpening and strengthening the tropopause. With the imminent end of the MLS mission, there is a strong need for continued vertically resolved water vapour profiles in the UTLS region. Impact studies performed within CAIRT Phase A have shown that the assimilation of CAIRT water vapour observations is quantitatively comparable to MLS in constraining water vapour in the UTLS region.

4.3.2 Ozone

Similar to water vapour, improving the representation of ozone in the UTLS has been shown to lead to improvements of meteorological predictions (Monge-Sanz et al., 2022). Impact studies performed within CAIRT Phase A have shown that the assimilation of CAIRT observations can constrain ozone in the UTLS region (and in particular the upper troposphere) even better than with MLS.

4.3.3 Temperature in the upper stratosphere and mesosphere

With the expected end of the TIMED/SABER observations, there is a need for continued observations of temperature in the mesosphere region.

4.3.4 AI in weather prediction

There is currently a revolution going on in the use of AI models for weather and climate prediction (e.g., (De Burgh-Day and Leeuwenburg, 2023). Currently methods are under development and still in their infancy to go directly from (sparse or satellite) observations to atmospheric analyses (e.g., (McNally et al., 2024) *preprint arXiv:2407.15586*; (Andrychowicz et al., 2023) *preprint arXiv:2306.06079*; (Huang et al., 2024) *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.05932*; (Keller and Potthast, 2024) *preprint arXiv:2406.00390*). It is very difficult to predict how this field will develop in the coming years, but it is clear that the training of AI models will require huge amount of data. The need for large volumes of data with spatially resolved atmospheric observations of many different parameters with near global coverage thus will likely even increase in the coming years with more and more use of AI methods.

4.4 Model validation

Validation of models and guidance of further model development is an important overall goal of CAIRT's science objectives. For chemistry climate models, the SPARC CCM-Val activities, that have now evolved in APARC's Chemistry Climate Modelling Initiative (CCMI), have paved the way for a process-oriented validation of models. The SPARC CCMVal-2 Report (SPARC Report No. 5, 2010) as already stated clear requirements and recommendations for future vertically resolved observations in the stratosphere and upper troposphere: "Long-term vertically resolved data sets of constituent observations in the stratosphere are required to assess model behavior and test model predictions. This includes ozone, but also other species that can be used to diagnose transport and chemistry. The current set of GCOS Essential Climate Variables is not sufficient for process-oriented validation of CCMs. More global vertically resolved observations are required, particularly in the UTLS. As CCMs evolve towards including tropospheric chemistry, lack of observations in this region will become a major limitation on model validation." Since the time of writing in 2010, the availability of vertically resolved data in the stratosphere and upper troposphere has not improved and these requirements are still valid. CAIRT's observational requirements and the assessed performance are aligned with these requirements and the expected impact of CAIRT data for model validation is well established.

4.5 Volcanic ash detection

Volcanic eruptions emit large amounts of gases and particles into the atmosphere (Fromm et al., 2014), causing severe impacts on atmosphere (Robock, 2000), climate (Robock, 2013), life on Earth (Forbes et al., 2003), human society (Robock, 2010); (Zehner, 2010) and aviation (Prata and Tupper, 2009).

The gases mostly present in volcanic clouds are H₂O, CO₂ and SO₂. In particular, SO₂, used often as a proxy for volcanic ash (Corradini et al., 2021), is considered potentially dangerous for aircraft engines while H₂O can lead to ice formation exploiting the ash particles as condensation nuclei. The volcanic ice clouds have been frequently observed also in many recent eruptions worldwide (Guerrieri et al., 2023); (Prata et al., 2020) and are considered extremely dangerous for aircraft because they are indistinguishable from meteorological clouds.

Volcanic ash clouds are well known to be very dangerous for aviation operations as they can cause damage to aircraft engines, abrading windscreens and damaging sensitive avionics equipment not only close to active volcanoes, but also at large distances from the eruption themselves. Recently, the 2010 Eyjafjallajökull eruption in Iceland forced the disruption of the airspace in several countries generating the largest air traffic shutdown since World War II and a loss of 3 billion euros by the airlines companies (Zehner, 2010). As a consequence of that, the "zero tolerance approach" (no flight possible everywhere the ash cloud is detected) has been replaced with the definition of an ash concentration threshold over which flying is not permitted. The current regulations in Europe state that airlines must have a safety case accepted by their national regulator to operate in concentrations of ash greater than 2 mg m⁻³ (Beckett et al., 2020).

The volcanic clouds are currently monitored by the International Airways Volcano Watch Operations Group (IAVWOPSG) of ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization), from the nine Volcanic Ash Advisory Centers (VAAC's) and from volcanic observatories exploiting ground-based, satellite and aircraft systems. Each of these systems has some temporal, spatial or technological limitations and only about 50% of the World's volcanoes that currently threaten air operations have any sort of ground-based monitoring ("IUGG Statement 'Volcanological and Meteorological Support for Volcanic Ash Monitoring,'" 2020).

In order to improve the flight security, there is an urgent need to get information on the vertical structure and composition of volcanic clouds as also stated in the ESA-EUMETSAT workshop on "Monitoring volcanic

ash from space” (Zehner, 2010) that came up with a list of recommendations including the suggestion that “Studies should be made of potential new satellites and instruments dedicated to monitoring volcanic ash plumes and eruptions” and that “there is an urgent need to gather information on the vertical structure of evolving volcanic clouds”.

In this framework, an accurate volcanic cloud geometry (altitude and thickness) retrieval represents a key task to be addressed, both for aviation safety and climatic studies. The cloud altitude is a crucial parameter because it constrains the ash-free altitude, while the thickness is necessary to compute the ash concentration starting from the ash columnar abundance (g/m^2) routinely obtained from satellite measurements (Clarisse and Prata, 2016). Also the Volcanic Ash Transport and Deposition Models (VATDM) will benefit from the improvement of the volcanic cloud altitude and thickness estimation being these input parameter necessary for the assimilation processes in order to produce reliable forecasts (Pardini et al., 2020).

Nowadays, the volcanic cloud top altitude can be retrieved with coarse accuracy and it is strictly related to the ash total mass ejected by the eruption (Corradini et al., 2018); (Merucci et al., 2016); (Settle, 1978). Moreover, multispectral and hyperspectral satellite systems cannot profile the atmosphere, or they can do it with very coarse vertical resolution only, then the cloud thickness remains a challenging parameter to be retrieved. Lidars are an alternative system that can be used to retrieve the thickness of the volcanic clouds with high vertical resolution, but the satellite lidars have low temporal resolution while the ground-based lidars are scattered with poor global coverage.

CAIRT can provide information on both altitude and thickness of volcanic clouds, thus improving the knowledge of volcanic ash concentration and the forecast of plume evolution. Furthermore, CAIRT should also be able to distinguish between ash and ice clouds thus contributing to mitigate the effect that these natural phenomena have on the environment and airspace.

4.6 Detecting and characterizing geoengineering by stratospheric particle injection

Anthropogenic greenhouse gases emissions are responsible for the presently observed climate change, associated with a series of effects on the climate system, the biosphere and societies (IPCC, 2021). To cope with the observed anthropogenic climate change and its effects, different solutions have been proposed, including mitigation, decarbonisation and adaptation. As a possible complementary solution, stratospheric aerosol geoengineering (SAG) has been proposed (Crutzen, 2006). Mimicking extreme volcanic eruptions, in SAG techniques sulphur dioxide (SO_2) is injected into the stratosphere with the aim of forming highly reflective and small-sized sulphate aerosol (SA) particles, through gas-to-particle conversion. The enhanced stratospheric SA burden can effectively scatter back a part of the incoming solar radiative flux, thus reducing the radiant energy income into the climate system, to counterbalance the reduction of outgoing longwave fluxes associated with the increase of greenhouse gases concentrations from anthropogenic emission. The amount and spatiotemporal location and sampling of the needed SO_2 injections strongly depends on the target to be achieved (e.g. which is the target surface temperature of the SAG application) and the considered scenario (e.g. which is the future socio-economical reference scenario and if and when complementary actions, like decarbonisation, are taken). On top of that, unwanted side effects are to be taken into account, like possible regional effects and induced inter-hemispheric and pole-to-equator gradients in surface temperature, which in turns can influence the climate system, e.g. through variation of tropical precipitation patterns (e.g. (MacMartin et al., 2017)). The enhancement of stratospheric SA in SAG interventions would also affect the stratospheric ozone layer, delaying the recovery from the Antarctic ozone hole phenomenology (Tilmes et al., 2022).

4.7 Detecting and characterizing the atmospheric impact of space debris

The impact of space transportation on the Earth's atmosphere is an emerging topic that recently has received considerable interest. This is largely motivated by the strong increase in the number of satellite launches projected for the coming decades, in particular from emerging and proposed large constellations. CAIRT can contribute to this topic by providing an improved picture of transport and background composition in the middle atmosphere from the stratosphere to the MLT region. This includes for example the characterization how material is transported from the MLT region in the winter polar regions into the stratosphere or the changes in ozone and other composition in the stratosphere. To what extent CAIRT can deliver also information on aerosols and their composition in the middle atmosphere and how they are impacted by space debris is still to be investigated. ((Ferreira et al., 2024); (Jackman et al., 1998); (Ross et al., 2009); (Ryan et al., 2022)).

4.8 The importance of the middle atmosphere for near Earth space

Observations of the middle atmosphere and its connection with the MLT and critical to better understand and predict how changes in atmospheric climate change and natural variability (in particular the solar cycle) will affect near Earth geospace (Mlynczak et al., 2021)). This has practical and direct relevance for the lifetime of the increasing fleet of small satellites in low and very low Earth orbit. The looming gap in observations of middle atmosphere composition and dynamics is of very real concern (Mlynczak et al., 2021). Still missing however, are a set of clear observation requirements and a prioritization of data products needed to address this concern.

4.9 Estimating Biosphere Gross Primary Production through observations of COS

Carbonyl sulfide (COS) has been suggested as a cotracer to estimate the gross primary production of eco systems. (Glatthor et al., 2015) DOI:10.1002/2015GL066293) and (Glatthor et al., 2017); DOI:10.5194/acp-17-2631-2017) have used MIPAS/ENVISAT observations to investigate the impact of plant uptake on upper tropospheric COS variability. Observational based climatologies, together with accompanying biogeochemical modelling, show variations in the tropical upper troposphere (at 250 hPa) of about +/- 30 ppt around a background of about 480 ppt.

5 Mission Objectives and Observation Requirements

5.1 Horizontal resolution

Most existing user requirement documents (e.g. GCOS, WMO, ESA CCI) stress the importance of trace gas observations in the UTLS and middle atmosphere at higher spatial (horizontal) resolution than available to date, with a goal at 50 km, a breakthrough at about 100 km, and a threshold of 200-400 km horizontal resolution. These user requirements for horizontal resolution are most mature for stratospheric ozone; attribution of ozone changes and variability requires that tracers for atmospheric transport and other factors influencing ozone are provided at the same or similar resolution. It is in fact interesting to note, that the 1966 NASA report on Satellite Meteorology (NASA SP96, 1966, p.1) made the following introductory statement: "It is generally agreed by meteorologists that ideal observations require measurement of wind, temperature, pressure and water-vapor content, as well as measurement of heat budget and the

concentration of the principal absorbers and emitters of radiation (CO₂, H₂O, and O₃), on a global grid of about 250 to 300 kilometers, from the surface up to 100 kilometers.”

5.2 Vertical resolution

The vertical resolution requirements for the different L2 targets slightly differ, depending on the science question to be addressed and the current state of knowledge. Generally, the required vertical resolution is highest in the UTLS region and decreases with increasing altitude. Most L2 targets have a goal vertical resolution of 1 km and a threshold of 2-3 km up to the lower mesosphere. This drives the requirement for vertical resolution of ≤ 1 km (goal, up to 80 km altitude) and ≤ 2 km threshold.

5.3 Geophysical data products at Level-2a

5.3.1 Temperature

Temperature is a very fundamental parameter for understanding essentially all of CAIRT’s science objectives, as well as a required for the retrieval of essentially all other Level 2 and higher level products. Consequently, temperature requirements are on the one hand side dictated by the need to achieve the requirements for the other L-2 products, and on the other hand to characterize atmospheric structure and variability to address the science topics, in particular the detection and characterization of atmospheric gravity waves. This means the required spatial resolution of the temperature product need to be as good or better than the required resolution of the other L-2 products. The most stringent requirement for the horizontal resolution comes from the requirement to resolve as much as possible of the gravity wave spectrum.

Table 10 Total uncertainty requirement for CAIRT L2 product temperature for goal (G) and threshold (T). For comparison, user requirements from OSCAR and GCOS (for goal/breakthrough/threshold) are included, as well as reported uncertainty for MIPAS/Envisat and MLS/Aura.

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	OSCAR G/B/T	GCOS-245 G/B/T	MIPAS	MLS	Importance
			(G)	(T)						
T	all	FT – LM	1	2	K	0.5/1/3	0.1/0.5/1	2-10	0.6 – 3.4	High
		UM	2	5		0.5/3/5		10-12	3.6 – 4	
		LT	10	20		10/14/20		-	-	

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-2: The need to resolve atmospheric gravity waves from temperature fluctuations in order to derive gravity wave momentum flux and drag is the driving requirement for temperature uncertainty, as well as spatial resolution.

SO-1 to SO-5: Temperature is an essential parameter for all CAIRT science objectives. Temperature indirectly affects the quality for essentially all other L2 and L2b products. As CAIRT uncertainty requirements capture essentially all the expected atmospheric variability up to the mesosphere and a substantial fraction of the expected variability in the MLT region (Figure 21), the temperature requirements are in line with needs for the Science Objectives SO-1 to SO-5.

Requirements for application objectives:

AO-1: Not directly relevant here.

AO-2: Not directly relevant here.

AO-3: Assimilation of CAIRT temperature observations will be of great benefit for numerical weather prediction (NWP). In particular as most weather centers have their model tops nowadays in the mesosphere, but there are very few temperature observations in the middle atmosphere (upper stratosphere and mesosphere) available. Requirements for NWP needs are formulated by GCOS-245. Temperature observations in the upper mesosphere and lower thermosphere are important for upper atmosphere data assimilation. The increased temperature and temperature variability in the MLT region justifies relaxed total uncertainty requirements for temperature in this region. CAIRT temperature total uncertainty requirements are broadly in line with user requirements as expressed by WMO OSCAR for the lower thermosphere (Table 10).

Broader User Requirements:

User requirements for atmospheric temperature have been summarized by GCOS-245 and are to be considered as mature for a wide range of applications. As temperature is such a fundamental parameter for the atmosphere, temperature information is essential for almost all applications.

Advancement over the state-of-the-art, present, upcoming and heritage instruments:

Table 10 includes uncertainty (precision only) for the past/current instruments MIPAS, ACE-FTS and MLS. It should however be noted that such a comparison can only be indicative, as the spatial resolution (vertical, horizontal in along track and across track dimensions) of the different instruments is different.

Requirement maturity and risks:

CAIRT temperature uncertainty requirements are mature and have been shown in first uncertainty assessments to be fit for purpose.

Recommendations:

CAIRT's temperature requirements are mature and fit for purpose.

Figure 20 Temperature distribution and variability computed from the Extended Reference Climatology (ERS). Orange: Range of climatological mean temperature profiles for different latitudes and seasons (MIN(MEAN) – MAX(MEAN)). Blue: Range of climatological temperature profiles plus/minus 3 standard deviations (MIN(MEAN-3STD) – MAX(MEAN+3STD)).

Figure 21 Temperature variability from the ERS climatology. Blue shading: Range of variability (1 standard deviation) for different latitudes and seasons. Black: CAIRT requirements.

5.3.2 Ozone

Table 11. Total uncertainty requirement for CAIRT L2 product O₃.

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	GCOS	O3 CCI	MIPAS	MLS	Importance
			(G)	(T)						
O ₃	5	FT	15 (8-42%)	30 (15-85%)	ppb	5/20	-	80%	20-30	M
		LS	50 (2%)	150 (5%)		150/600	250	25%	30-60	H
		US	100 (2%)	200 (4%)		250/1000	425	20%	150-400	H
		LM	50 (8%)	100 (15%)		30/120	50	20-50%	400-1100	M
		UM	100 (8-34%)	300 (25-100%)		50/250	-	-	1100-3400	M

Conversion between absolute and relative uncertainty is based on the BRS profile (Table 13 below).

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-5: The primary driving mission requirement for ozone is MO-P-5, to quantify the vertical and horizontal distribution of O₃ (and H₂O) throughout the middle atmosphere, with particular emphasis on resolving strong gradients and spatial features within the upper troposphere-lower stratosphere (UTLS). A quantitative justification for the required total uncertainty to resolve these features is based on the expected ozone variability in the different altitude regions (Figure 23).

SO-1: Circulation and mixing can be deduced also from small scale ozone variations. Similar requirements as for MO-P-5 apply. This is in particular relevant in the UTLS region and across the tropopause. In the upper troposphere it is important to detect ozone enhancements from the stratosphere against the tropospheric background of ~35 ppb.

SO-2: Not relevant here.

SO-3: Investigating upper atmosphere coupling through the impact of NO_y on stratospheric ozone requires to detect ozone changes in the mesosphere of 15-30% and in the stratosphere of a few percent (e.g., (Sinnhuber et al., 2018) Fig. 12). Spatial averages (like vortex mean or polar cap mean) will be sufficient here to reduce the uncertainty if needed.

SO-4: Investigating the coupling with the lower atmosphere and the impact of pollutants and aerosols (e.g. from biomass burning plumes) requires ozone observations in the lower stratosphere with a total uncertainty of about 100 ppb (e.g., (Solomon et al., 2023), Fig. 2).

SO-5: Attribution of ozone changes due to chemistry and transport requires observation of ozone with a total uncertainty within the expected changes, in line with the requirements. To detect and attribute stratospheric ozone profiles changes on decadal timescales, expected to be in the range of a few percent per decade (e.g., WMO, 2022, Figs. 3-11 and 3-12), requires a total uncertainty of ozone in the stratosphere of about 3%, where spatial and temporal averages (e.g. monthly zonal means) would be sufficient.

Requirements for application objectives:

AO-1: Retrieval of tropospheric ozone (profile or column) by synergistic limb-nadir combination strongly benefits from stratospheric and UTLS ozone profile information. GCOS-245 (2022, Table 3.2.4) provides user requirements for the measurement uncertainty (2-sigma) of tropospheric ozone columns of 5 and 15% for goal and threshold, respectively. A quantitative analysis for the required stratospheric profile uncertainty is to be done.

AO-2: Not directly relevant here.

AO-3: Requirements for assimilation of ozone in numerical weather forecasting and air quality models are reflected by the GCOS-245 (2022) user requirements included in Table 11 above.

Broader User Requirements:

User requirements for ozone mixing ratio profile uncertainty are provided by GCOS-245 (2022), GAW-159 (2004) and the ESA O3 CCI User Requirements Document, included in Table 11 above. GCOS-245 (2022) states a threshold requirement for horizontal resolution of 200 km in the UTLS (their Table 3.2.2) and of 500 km in the upper stratosphere and mesosphere (their Table 3.2.3).

Advancement over the state-of-the-art, present, upcoming and heritage instruments:

A number of previous satellite missions have provided vertical profiles of ozone in the upper troposphere to mesosphere. Of particular relevance here are MIPAS on ENVISAT (2002-2012) and MLS on Aura (since 2004), included in Table 11 above. Values given are measurement precision for single profile observations. A more comprehensive table, including also ACE-FTS and OMPS is included in Table 12 below.

Table 12. Ozone profile uncertainty for selected heritage instruments.

Product	Altitude region	ACE-FTS	MIPAS	MLS			OMPS
				precision		accuracy	
				abs	rel		
O3	FT	15-20 %	80 %	0.02 - 0.03 ppmv	5 - 100 %	10 %	10-20 %
	LS	3-10 %	25 %	0.03 - 0.06 ppmv	2 - 30 %	5 - 7 %	15-20 %
	US	2-5 %	20 %	0.15 - 0.4 ppmv	2 - 30 %	7 - 10 %	7 %
	LM	5-10 %	20-50 %	0.4 - 1.1 ppmv	20 - 500 %	8 - 100 %	8 %
	UM	10-20 %	n/a	1.1 - 3.4 ppmv	40 - 500 %	30 - 100 %	n/a

Requirement maturity and risks:

CAIRT ozone profile requirements derived from SO-5 / MO-P-5 are well in line with existing user requirements such as GCOS, GAW and the ESA O3 CCI. CAIRT's requirements for ozone profile total uncertainty are in line or better than what was achieved from existing, past or upcoming satellite instruments, at a higher horizontal and vertical resolution, in line with various user requirements (e.g. GCOS). Accuracy, bias and stability requirements to detect long-term changes are compatible with the total uncertainty requirement but may be challenged.

Recommendations:

CAIRT ozone profile requirements are mature and fit for purpose.

Figure 22. O₃ distribution and variability computed from the Extended Reference Climatology (ERS). Orange: Range of climatological mean O₃ profiles for different latitudes and seasons (MIN(MEAN) – MAX(MEAN)). Blue: Range of climatological O₃ profiles plus/minus 3 standard deviations (MIN(MEAN-3STD) – MAX(MEAN+3STD)). Black: CAIRT requirements.

Figure 23. O₃ variability from the ERS climatology. Blue shading: Range of variability (1 standard deviation) for different latitudes and seasons. Black: CAIRT requirements.

Table 13. BRS climatology (April 45°N)

Altitude Range	VMR Day (ppb)	VMR Night (ppb)
FT	100 (35 – 200)	100 (35 – 200)
LS	3100	3100
US	5300	5300
LM	660	1100
UM	290	1200
LT	60	800

5.3.3 Water vapour

Uncertainty requirements for water vapour are often expressed in percentage. To convert between mixing ratios in ppmv and percentage, stratospheric H₂O is around 5ppmv (3 – 6 ppmv), so that 10% correspond to

about 0.5ppmv. Free tropospheric H₂O is much larger and can exhibit a large variability. The BRS value in the FT is around 500ppm.

Table 14 Total uncertainty requirement for CAIRT L2 product H₂O.

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	GCOS-245	WV CCI	MIPAS	MLS
			(G)	(T)		G/T	G/B/T		
H ₂ O	5	FT	5	10	%	5(*)	-	12-15	6-16
		LS	5	10	%	2/10	1/5/25	10-15	5-7
		US	5	10	%	2/10	1/5/25	10	5-17
		LM	500	800	ppb	100/500		10-50%	17-60%
		UM	500	800	ppb	100/500		-	>60%

(*) based on GCOS-200 (2016)

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-5: Water vapour requirements follow directly from CAIRT MO-P-5 to observe the distribution of water vapour throughout the middle atmosphere. Requirements for total uncertainties in the free troposphere to upper stratosphere of 5% (goal) and 10% (threshold) are in line with GCOS-245 threshold requirements and within the ESA water vapour (WV) CCI user requirements of 5% (breakthrough) and 25% (goal) for the stratosphere.

SO-1: Water vapour can further support the diagnosis of atmospheric transport and circulation. Total water in the middle atmosphere (the sum of H₂O and 2 α CH₄, where α is the fractional release factor, Hegglin et al., 2014) has been used to infer changes of age-of-air in the stratosphere (Garny et al., 2024). Interannual variability in stratospheric water vapour due to changes in atmospheric circulation is in the order of 0.5 ppm peak-to-peak (Tao et al., 2023), with long-term trends in the order of 10%/decade.

SO-2: Not directly relevant.

SO-3: Subsidence of air from the upper atmosphere into the stratosphere may be supported by total water observations, see SO-1 above.

SO-4: Lofting of tropospheric air into the lower stratosphere (and stratosphere-troposphere exchange in general) can be diagnosed from water observations. Volcanic eruptions (like in particular the Hunga-Tonga eruption) can transport large quantities of water into the middle atmosphere.

Requirements for application objectives:

AO-3: Accurate water vapour observations in the lower stratosphere are of critical importance for numerical weather prediction. User requirements for NWP are reflected by GCOS-245.

Broader User Requirements:

User requirements for water vapour measurements are given by GCOS and ESA's WV CCI (Table 14).

Advancement over the state-of-the-art, present, upcoming and heritage instruments:

CAIRT total uncertainty threshold requirements are broadly consistent with uncertainties achieved for passed or current limb missions, in particular MIPAS and MLS (Table 14). It should be noted, however, that the uncertainties given for these other missions are only for precision (i.e. not including any systematic bias) and depend directly on the spatial resolution, which is not identical to the CAIRT requirements.

Requirement maturity and risks:

Water vapour total uncertainty requirements are in line with existing user requirements and correspond to – or even go beyond – the state of the art from previous limb missions. However, the threshold total uncertainty requirements are only at the upper range of expected water vapour variability in the upper stratosphere and mesosphere (Figure 25). In the UTLS region current requirements are mature, while in the upper stratosphere and mesosphere there is some risk that the current requirements may be challenged.

Figure 24 H₂O distribution and variability computed from the Extended Reference Climatology (ERS). Orange: Range of climatological mean H₂O profiles for different latitudes and seasons (MIN(MEAN) – MAX(MEAN)). Blue: Range of climatological H₂O profiles plus/minus 3 standard deviations (MIN(MEAN-3STD) – MAX(MEAN+3STD)). Black: CAIRT requirements.

Figure 25 H₂O variability from the ERS climatology. Blue shading: Range of variability (1 standard deviation) within different latitude regions and seasons. Black: CAIRT requirements.

5.3.4 Age-of-air and long-lived trace gases

To diagnose atmospheric circulation and transport by age-of-air in the lower stratosphere is a primary CAIRT mission objective. CAIRT MO-P-1 specifies the requirement to observe age-of-air at a total uncertainty of less than 0.5 years, to achieve a scientific breakthrough. Age-of-air will be derived from SF₆ on an absolute scale and can be transferred to the 100 km sale by the use of other long-lived trace gases. The requirements for the other long-lived trace gases are derived from the correlation with age-of-air, as elaborated in Section

2.1. N₂O, CH₄ and HCFC-22 can be used to extend the derivation of age-of-air into the upper stratosphere above 30 km altitude. In the upper stratosphere and mesosphere, CH₄ and CO will be used to diagnose transport from the MLT region (see Section 2.3).

Table 15 Total uncertainty requirement for CAIRT L2 product long-lived trace gases.

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	LOLIPOP	MIPAS	ACE-FTS	Importance
			(G)	(T)					
SF ₆	1	LS	0.05	0.15	ppt	1%/10% (0.1/1ppt)	30-80%	unknown	High

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	GAW-159	GCOS	MIPAS	MLS	Importance
			(G)	(T)						
N ₂ O	1	LS	5 (2-5%)	15 (5-16%)	ppb	2/4.3/20	0.05/0.1/0.3	8-15%	12-15 (4-11%)	High
		US	5 (6->100%)	15 (20->100%)					15-20%	15-18 (11-100%)

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	GAW-159	LOLIPOP	MIPAS	Importance
			(G)	(T)					
CFC-11	1	LS	10	25	ppt	5/10%	2-5% / 10%	10-70%	Medium
CFC-12	1	LS	10	30	ppt	5/10%	2-5% / 10%	15-30%	High
HCFC-22	1	LS	2	6	ppt	-	2-5% / 10%	15-80%	High

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	GCOS-245	GAW-159	MIPAS	ACE-FTS	Importance
			(G)	(T)						
CH ₄	1	LS	30	60	ppb	1/5	2/10	10-15%	5%	H
		US							5-8%	H
		LM							5-8%	H

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	GCOS-245	GCOS-200	MIPAS	MLS	Importance
			(G)	(T)						
CO	1, 4	FT	10	30	ppb	1/5/10	20% (~20ppb)	10%	19 ppb	M
		LS	10	30		1/5/10			9-19 ppb	L
		US	40	70		-	30-50%	16-640 ppb	H	
		LM	100	500		-	25%	640-3400ppb	H	
		UM	700	2000		-	25%	3400-12000ppb	H	
		LT	2000	5000		-	-	-	-	

(BRS: CO in FT ~100ppb -> 20% are about 20ppb.)

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-1: The requirements for measurements of long-lived trace gases follows directly from the requirement to observe age-of-air as a diagnostic for atmospheric transport and circulation. To capture relevant variability at the 100 km scale, as well as to detect changes on longer (intra-seasonal to decadal) time scales, age-of-air needs to be detected with a total uncertainty of ≤ 0.5 years (≤ 0.25 years in monthly zonal means). In the mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT), where the concept of age-of-air is not well developed, CH₄ and CO are required to detect and quantify changes in transport.

SO-2: Not directly relevant

SO-3: Long-lived tracers, in particular CO and CH₄, are critical to quantify the transport of NO_y from the MLT region into the stratosphere.

SO-4: Long-lived tracers, in particular N₂O and CFCs, are important to diagnose stratosphere-troposphere exchange.

SO-5: Attribution of stratospheric ozone changes critically depends on a quantification of transport changes. Moreover, the CFCs as well as N₂O are important ozone depleting substances. Knowledge on their atmospheric distribution and temporal changes are key for attribution of ozone changes.

Broader User Requirements:

User requirements for long-lived trace gases are available from GCOS and most recently from the ESA Lolipop assessment. However, the different scientific applications and corresponding user needs of these requirements are not always clearly spelled out in the existing requirement assessments.

Advancement over the state-of-the-art, present, upcoming and heritage instruments:

Vertical resolved observations of long-lived trace gases have been provided by the UARS instruments MLS, HALOE, CLAES, by MIPAS-ENVISAT, Aura-MLS, and ACE-FTS. There are no scheduled future missions to provide these observations. Requirements formulated for CAIRT are broadly in line with what has been achieved with these previous limb missions.

Requirement maturity and risks:

There is significant diversity in published user requirements, reflecting different purposes and applications. CAIRT requirements are derived primarily towards the goals of SO-1 and with respect to the existing state-of-the-art.

Recommendations:

CAIRT Phase 0 MATER and RfA have specified for N₂O a goal vertical resolution of 2 km in the US. We recommend to change this to 1 km goal, but retaining the threshold of 3 km.

Requirements for HCFC-22 so far formulated only for the LS can be extended for the US with the same specifications.

a

b

Figure 26 Long-lived trace gases (**a.** SF₆, **b.** N₂O, **c.** CFC-11, **d.** CFC-12, **e.** HCFC-22, **f.** CH₄, **g.** CO) distribution and variability computed from the Extended Reference Climatology (ERS). Orange: Range of climatological mean profiles for different latitudes and seasons (MIN(MEAN) – MAX(MEAN)). Blue: Range of climatological profiles plus/minus 3 standard deviations (MIN(MEAN-3STD) – MAX(MEAN+3STD)). Black: CAIRT requirements.

a

b

c

d

e

Figure 27 Long-lived trace gases (a. SF₆, b. N₂O, c. CFC-11, d. CFC-12, e. HCFC-22, f. CH₄, g. CO) variability from the ERS climatology. Blue shading: Range of variability (1 standard deviation) for different latitudes and seasons. Black: CAIRT requirements.

5.3.5 Nitrogen species

Observation requirements for nitrogen species are motivated by the need to observe the flux of nitrogen oxides (NO_y) from the lower thermosphere into the stratosphere. NO_y is primarily composed of NO, NO₂, HNO₃, N₂O₅ and ClONO₂. Other gases like HNO₄ are only minor contributors. The fraction of the individual contributors to NO_y changes with altitude, which is reflected in the requirement Table 16.

Table 16. Total uncertainty requirements for CAIRT L2 nitrogen species.

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	GAW-159	MIPAS	Importance
			(G)	(T)				
NO	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	5/10%	n/a	M
		US	0.2	1		5/10%	10-30 %	H
		LM	2	20		10/30%	20-50%	H
		UM	100	600		10/30%	40-80%	H
		LT	5000	30000		10/30%	30-40%	H
NO ₂	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	5/10%	25-70%	M
		US	0.2	0.5		5/10%	50-100%	H
		LM	2	5		n/a	100 %	H
HNO ₃	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	5/10%	15-40%	H
		US	0.2	0.5		5/10%	10-100 %	H
		LM	0.5	2		n/a	n/a	H
N ₂ O ₅	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	n/a	40-80%	M
		US				n/a	40-100%	M
ClONO ₂	3	LS	0.1	0.25	ppb	5/10%	40-80%	M
		US	0.2	0.5		5/10%	40-200%	M

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-3: Requirements for the observation of nitrogen species follow from CAIRT’s mission objective MO-P-3 to observe NO produced in the lower thermosphere and NO_x (NO, NO₂) in the MLT during quiescent conditions and during geomagnetic storms, and quantify the total reactive nitrogen NO_y (NO_x, HNO₃, N₂O₅, ClONO₂) throughout the stratosphere. To observe the flux of nitrogen species from the MLT region into the stratosphere requires the observation of the main contributors of NO_y, that is NO, NO₂, HNO₃, N₂O₅ and

ClONO₂. NO is produced in the MLT region by interaction with solar and geomagnetic variability. NO is the dominant NO_y species in the MLT region, so drives requirements there. In the stratosphere the partitioning of NO_y depends on atmospheric region, season and time of day; uniform requirements for uncertainty and spatial resolution of the main NO_y species in the stratosphere simplify the diagnosis of NO_y as a L2b product.

SO-1: NO_y can also be used as a diagnostic for atmospheric transport.

SO-2: Not directly relevant

SO-4: Changes in the stratospheric particle loading, e.g. from volcanic eruptions, biomass burning or other contributors, critically affect the NO_y partitioning. Observation of the individual NO_y species (and their partitioning) are therefore also an important indicator for changes in atmospheric chemistry, including adverse effects from potential geoengineering.

SO-5: NO_y plays an important role in atmospheric (ozone) chemistry. Requirements formulated for MO-P-3 are in line with requirements for atmospheric chemistry. Chlorine nitrate is also an important halogen species involved in stratospheric ozone chemistry. To take into account the needs to characterize chlorine catalyzed ozone chemistry, uncertainty requirements for ClONO₂ have been formulated more stringent than otherwise needed to quantify NO_y.

Broader User Requirements:

GAW-159 list requirements of 5% (goal) / 10% (threshold) for NO, NO₂, HNO₃ and ClONO₂ in the stratosphere. In addition GAW-159 specifies NO requirements in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere of 10/30%.

a

b

Figure 28 Nitrogen species (a. NO, b. NO₂, c. HNO₃, d. N₂O₅, e. ClONO₂) distribution and variability computed from the Extended Reference Climatology (ERS). Orange: Range of climatological mean profiles for different latitudes and seasons (MIN(MEAN) – MAX(MEAN)). Blue: Range of climatological profiles plus/minus 3 standard deviations (MIN(MEAN-3STD) – MAX(MEAN+3STD)). Black: CAIRT requirements.

Figure 29 Nitrogen species (a. NO, b. NO₂, c. HNO₃, e. N₂O₅, f. ClONO₂) variability from the ERS climatology. Blue shading: Range of variability (1 standard deviation) for different latitudes and seasons. Black: CAIRT requirements. ERS does not reflect mesospheric HNO₃ enhancements. Figure 24d shows MIPAS HNO₃ enhancement (Funke et al., 2011).

5.3.6 Aerosols, precursors and pollutants

Table 17. Total uncertainty requirements for CAIRT level 2 sulfur species.

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	GAW-159	MIPAS	MLS	Importance
			(G)	(T)					
H ₂ SO ₄ (l)	4	LS	0.1	0.3	μm ³ /cm ³				High
SO ₂	4	LS	0.1	1	ppb	0.01/0.02	30-100%	3.6 – 5.8	High
COS	4	LS	0.05	0.15	ppb	15%/25%	30-90%		Medium

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-4: Requirements for sulfur species in the lower stratosphere follow directly from CAIRT Mission Objective 4 to quantify sulfate aerosol and the atmospheric sulfur budget (H₂SO₄(l), SO₂, OCS) within the free

troposphere and the lower stratosphere during background and enhanced conditions. Requirements for SO₂ and H₂SO₄ as specified in Table 17 will enable detection and quantification for enhanced levels following volcanic eruptions. Volcanic eruption plumes require observation at horizontal scales of about 100 km. Detection and quantification of SO₂ and H₂SO₄ at background conditions will require lower total uncertainty, but can well be achieved at larger horizontal scales (such as zonal averages). This is expressed by the user requirements from GAW-159 for SO₂, but currently not reflected in the CAIRT requirements. OCS requirements as specified in Table 17 will enable characterization of the basic features of OCS. More recent OCS observations (M. von Hobe, personal communication) show significant variability in the UTLS of about +/- 100pptv at horizontal scales of about 100 km, further underpinning the specified requirements, see also Karu et al 2023; Ma et al. 2021.

SO-1: Not directly relevant

SO-2: Not directly relevant

SO-3: Not directly relevant

SO-5: Knowledge about the stratospheric sulfur loading is critical to attribute changes in ozone and broader chemistry.

Requirements for application objectives:

COS is an important co-tracer for biogenic uptake of carbon, as it behaves similar to CO₂. Glatthor et al. (2015) investigated the variability in the upper troposphere due to biogenic uptake using MIPAS observations. Observed variability in the tropical upper troposphere is around 40ppt, which required MIPAS monthly mean averages to achieve the sufficient precision.

Broader User Requirements:

GAW-159 for SO₂ of 15/18/25%.

Advancement over the state-of-the-art, present, upcoming and heritage instruments:

Sulfur requirements as formulated in Table 17 would lead to an improvement over past limb missions.

Requirement maturity and risks:

CAIRT requirements are specified for enhanced (volcanic) conditions. Observation under background conditions would require spatial or temporal averaging. This has not been considered so far.

Recommendations:

Specify also requirements for SO₂ and H₂SO₄ for background conditions (i.e. at lower total uncertainty) and reduced spatial resolution (e.g. zonal averages).

Figure 30 Sulfur species (**a.** H₂SO₄(l), **b.** SO₂, **c.** COS) distribution and variability computed from the Extended Reference Climatology (ERS). Orange: Range of climatological mean profiles for different latitudes and seasons (MIN(MEAN) – MAX(MEAN)). Blue: Range of climatological profiles plus/minus 3 standard deviations (MIN(MEAN-3STD) – MAX(MEAN+3STD)). Black: CAIRT requirements.

Figure 31 Sulfur species (a. H₂SO₄(l), b. SO₂, c. COS) variability from the ERS climatology. Blue shading: Range of variability (1 standard deviation) for different latitudes and seasons. Black: CAIRT requirements.

Table 18. Total uncertainty requirements for pollutants PAN and CO.

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	GCOS G/T	MIPAS	MLS	Importance
			(G)	(T)					
PAN	4	FT – LS	0.04	0.1	ppb	NA	15-25%	NA	M
CO	4	FT	10	30	ppb	20% (*)	10%	19	M
		LS	10	30			10-75%		M

(*) BRS: CO in FT ~100ppb -> 20% are about 20ppb.

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-4: Requirements for sulfur species in the lower stratosphere follow directly from CAIRT Mission Objective 4 to quantify pollutants from biomass burning and anthropogenic origins (CO, PAN). Requirements for PAN are based on heritage with the GLORIA airborne instrument and results from MIPAS/Envisat. MLS observations of biomass burning in the stratosphere showed enhancement in plumes of well over 100ppb (Section 2.4.1, p.26).

SO-1 to SO-3: not directly relevant

SO-5: Knowledge of pollution tracers will provide critical information for assessing ozone chemistry in the UTLS region, to attribute observed ozone changes.

Requirements for application objectives:

Broader User Requirements:

User requirements for CO in the UTLS region have been formulated by GCOS / GAW. No previous user requirements for PAN exist.

Advancement over the state-of-the-art, present, upcoming and heritage instruments:

Requirements for CO and PAN reflect the state-of-the-art from previous limb missions (goal requirements).

Figure 32 Sulfur species (a. PAN, b. CO) distribution and variability computed from the Extended Reference Climatology (ERS). Orange: Range of climatological mean profiles for different latitudes and seasons (MIN(MEAN) – MAX(MEAN)). Blue: Range of climatological profiles plus/minus 3 standard deviations (MIN(MEAN-3STD) – MAX(MEAN+3STD)). Black: CAIRT requirements.

Figure 33 Sulfur species (a. PAN, b. CO) variability from the ERS climatology. Blue shading: Range of variability (1 standard deviation) for different latitudes and seasons. Black: CAIRT requirements.

5.3.7 Summary L2 requirements

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	Vert. res. (km)		Hor. res (km)	
			(G)	(T)		(G)	(T)	(G)	(T)
T	all	FT – LM	1	2	K	1	2	50	200
		UM	2	5		2	4	200	400
		LT	10	20		4	7	200	400
H ₂ O	5	FT	5	10	%	1	2	100	200
		LS	5	10	%	1	3	100	200
		US	5	10	%	2	3	100	300
		LM	500	800	ppb	2	4	200	400
		UM	500	800	ppb	3	5	200	400
O ₃	5	FT	15	30	ppb	1	2	100	200
		LS	50	150		1	2	100	200
		US	100	200		2	3	100	200
		LM	50	100		2	4	200	300
		UM	100	300		2	5	200	400
CH ₄	1	LS	30	60	ppb	1	3	100	200
		US				2	3	100	200
		LM				2	4	200	300
SF ₆	1	LS	0.1	0.13	ppt	1	3	100	ZM
HCFC-22	1	LS	2	6	ppt	1	3	100	200
CFC-11	1	LS	10	25	ppt	1	3	100	200
CFC-12	1	LS	10	30	ppt	1	3	100	200
N ₂ O	1	LS	10	16	ppb	1	3	100	200
		US				2			
CO	1, 4	FT	20	30	ppb	1	2	100	200
		LS	20	30		1	2	100	200
		US	40	70		2	3	200	300
		LM	100	500		2	4	200	300
		UM	700	2000		3	5	200	400
		LT	2000	5000		4	7	200	400
NO	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	1	4	100	300
		US	0.2	1		2	4	200	300
		LM	2	20		2	4	200	300
		UM	100	600		3	5	200	400
		LT	5000	30000		3	5	200	400
NO ₂	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	1	3	100	300
		US	0.2	0.5		2	3	200	
		LM	2	5		2	4	200	
HNO ₃	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	1	3	100	300
		US	0.2	0.5		2	3	200	300
		LM	0.5	2		2	4	200	400
N ₂ O ₅	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	1	3	100	300
		US				2		200	
ClONO ₂	3	LS	0.1	0.25	ppb	1	3	100	300
		US	0.2	0.5		2		200	
PAN	4	FT – LS	0.04	0.1	ppb	1	2	100	200
OCS	4	LS	0.05	0.15	ppb	1	2	100	200
SO ₂	4	LS	0.1	1	ppb	1	2	100	200
H ₂ SO ₄ (l)	4	LS	0.1	0.3	µm ³ /cm ³	1	2	100	200

5.4 Geophysical data products at Level-2b

5.4.1 Gravity wave products

Variable	content	unit	Uncertainty	Vertical range
λ_z	vertical wavelengths	[km]	10%	LS-UM
λ_h	horizontal wavelength	[km]	10%	LS-UM
α	wave direction	[deg], clockwise from N	10°	LS-UM
<i>Tamp</i>	temperature amplitude	[K]	15%	LS-UM
GWMF (F)	vertical flux of horizontal momentum	[Pa]	30%	LS-UM
<i>cϕ,intr</i>	intrinsic phase speed	[ms ⁻¹]		LS-UM
<i>cϕ,gb</i>	ground-based phase-speed	[ms ⁻¹]	5 m/s	LS-UM

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-2: Requirements for gravity wave products follow directly from CAIRT MO-P-2 to determine the global distribution of gravity wave momentum flux and drag by resolving wave length, phase speed, and direction of gravity waves in a range of ~100 to ~2000 km horizontal and down to $\lesssim 3$ km vertical wavelengths, from the lower stratosphere into the mid-mesosphere.

Requirement maturity and risks:

Gravity wave products have not been available in this form from previous (heritage) missions. There is thus little previous experience.

5.4.2 Age-of-air

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	Vert. res. (km)		Hor. res. (km)	
			(G)	(T)		(G)	(T)	(G)	(T)
Age-of-air	1	LS	0.25	0.5	years	1	3	100	200
				0.25					

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-1: Requirements for age-of-air follow directly from CAIRT's mission objective MO-P-1 to observe atmospheric circulation throughout the lower stratosphere via long-lived tracers and derived age-of-air with a total uncertainty of $\lesssim 0.5$ years ($\lesssim 0.25$ years in monthly zonal means).

Requirement maturity and risks:

Expected long-term changes in age-of-air are at 0.25 years for broader atmospheric regions, so that the required total uncertainty of 0.25 years (for zonal means) is really to be understood as a threshold; a lower total uncertainty such as 0.1 years for zonal means would reduce the risk.

5.4.3 NO_y

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	Vert. res. (km)		Hor. res. (km)	
			(G)	(T)		(G)	(T)	(G)	(T)
NO _y	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	1	3	100	300
		US							

Requirements derived from CAIRT Science Mission Objectives:

MO-P-3: Requirements for NO_y follow directly from CAIRT's mission objective MO-P-3 to quantify the total reactive nitrogen NO_y (NO, NO₂, HNO₃, N₂O₅, ClONO₂) throughout the stratosphere. They have been directly carried over from the corresponding L2 requirements for the individual NO_y species.

Requirement maturity and risks: The requirements are mature and based on heritage from past observations.

5.5 Altitude coverage

CAIRT's science objectives require observations over a large altitude region from the upper troposphere to the lower thermosphere. The lower altitude limit is essentially determined by the altitude when the atmosphere becomes optically thick at infra-red wavelength, so that observations below this altitude are not useful anymore.

The upper limit of CAIRT's altitude range is motivated by the need to resolve the concentration maximum of nitric oxide (NO) in the lower thermosphere just above 100 km altitude (Figure 12). A minimum altitude of 105 km (threshold) or better of 115 km (goal) is required to resolve this NO concentration maximum which serves as an upper boundary to derive the flux of nitrogen oxides (NO_y) into the middle atmosphere.

5.6 Latitude coverage

Most of CAIRT's primary science questions and applications are not limited to specific regions but inherently global in nature. CAIRT thus requires essentially global observations over as large of a latitude range as possible with no systematic outages at specific locations. Much of the important science takes place at high latitudes of both hemispheres: this includes the production of nitrogen oxide in the lower thermosphere within the auroral oval (Figure 12), the subsidence of thermospheric and mesospheric air into the polar vortex (Figure 13), stratospheric ozone depletion inside the polar vortex (Figure 18) and Ozone Hole, the propagation of atmospheric gravity waves in high latitudes and their interaction with the polar vortex, and the dynamical downward propagation of polar vortex anomalies on tropospheric weather. It is thus important that CAIRT has a good coverage of the auroral oval and polar vortex. Climatologically the polar vortex edge is at about 70° latitude in both hemispheres, requiring CAIRT observations sufficiently poleward of 70°. There are also within the polar vortex systematic differences in conditions, e.g. associated with the darkness of polar night within the terminator, that require observations not only in the polar vortex edge region, but ideally over a large latitudinal range. A sun-synchronous orbit, required for comparability of longer-term observations and for collocated observations with the METOP-SG nadir sounders, would enable observations up to about 83° of latitude of both hemispheres, compatible with the requirement to cover the polar regions. Important ground-based validation sites in the Arctic are located at Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen (79°N) and the Polar Environmental Atmospheric Research Laboratory (PEARL) at Eureka, Canada (80°N).

5.7 Across track coverage (swath width)

Driving requirement for the across track coverage is Science Objective 3, quantification of gravity waves. According to our experience, with an across-track of 300 km it should be possible to determine wave parameters for GWs up to 1500km wavelengths and thus almost the entire range to the long-end side of the horizontal wavelength spectrum. Horizontal propagation of a single wave event requires to capture a volume substantially larger than a typical wavelength (e.g. 150-200 km).

The need to resolve filamentary structures in trace gases and age-of-air in the stratosphere at horizontal spatial scales of about 100 km in extent requires an across track width of at least 300 km to identify these filaments also in the across-track dimension.

In addition, there is the general strong benefit of a wide across track coverage to increase the probability for observation of specific events of interest (such as plumes from volcanic eruptions, biomass burning and similar), as well as enhancing the probability to encounter cloud free areas for observations into the mid- to upper troposphere. In particular, these events and their in-mixing into the lowermost stratosphere as well as filaments facilitating the mixing as second component of the BDC can be quantified from identical air masses repeatedly on subsequent days. The likelihood for thus multiple observations increases with the across track width.

The across track width is directly related to the time needed to achieve global coverage.

5.8 Operational lifetime

The duration of the CAIRT mission requires a minimum of 5 years to cover inter-annual variability in relation to climate modes such as the Arctic or Antarctic Oscillations or North Atlantic Oscillation, Quasi-Biennial Oscillation and the El Niño Southern Oscillation. An optional mission extension beyond the five years would obviously be highly beneficial to observe longer-term changes and to provide measurement continuity. Moreover, an extended mission lifetime enhances the probability to observe rare events like explosive volcanic eruptions.

5.9 Product latency

Assimilation of CAIRT data into NWP and air quality models is not only an important application to improve forecasts, but has a number of additional benefits: near real time data assimilation helps in identifying and improving biases (or other kind of problems) in the observations and helps to link CAIRT data to other data sets. Near real time data assimilation also provides the incentives and the establishment of a work flow for CAIRT assimilation that can be exploited for reanalyses: experience tells that it is unlikely that a new satellite instrument is included in climate reanalyses that has not been included before for NRT assimilation.

While it ultimately is desirable to assimilate spectral radiances (L1b data) instead of retrieved products (L2a data), for the foreseeable future there is also the need to assimilate retrieved L2 products. Bormann and Thépaut (Assimilation of MIPAS limb radiances in the ECMWF system, (Bormann and Thépaut, 2006)) have described the assimilation of MIPAS limb radiances into the ECMWF system. CAIRT near real time data will be most useful to constrain temperature in the upper stratosphere and in particular water vapour and ozone in the lower stratosphere, where there are currently large biases in water vapour in the analyses, leading to a temperature bias.

The current generation of the data assimilation system at ECMWF considers satellite observations within a 6 hour time window (Elias Holm, ECMWF, personal communication, 2025).

5.10 Formation flying

As a stand-alone mission, CAIRT will provide unique information on temperature and atmospheric composition from 5 km to 115 km with unprecedented vertical and horizontal resolution. Flying the CAIRT mission in loose formation with the EUMETSAT MetOp-SG-A1 satellite offers additional benefits, by allowing:

- to extend profiling into the lower troposphere with improved accuracy with respect to nadir measurements alone and with the possibility of exploring links to surface emission and air quality,

- to take advantage of the high horizontal resolution of nadir measurements to provide to the CAIRT retrieval additional information on the horizontal variation of the atmosphere in the troposphere.

Synergy will be considered with both IASI-NG and Sentinel-5 instruments on board of MetOp-SG-A satellite, but due to the similar spectral range of IASI-NG and CAIRT, a deeper investigation will be done with IASI-NG measurements which allow to consider a larger number of species.

In addition, loose formation with MetOp-SG-A would enable synergies with METimage observations of clouds and ground scenes (e.g., in the context of volcanic or biomass burning plumes).

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Appendix: Science Traceability Matrix

The connections between the CAIRT Science Objectives with the Challenges defined in ESA's Living Planet 2016 Earth Observation Science Strategy as well as the flowdown from CAIRT Science Objectives to CAIRT Mission Objectives and further to geophysical requirements is illustrated in the following Science Traceability Matrix:

